

IMPROVED TRANSDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE
FOR EFFECTIVE ECOSYSTEM-BASED
MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING AND
CONSERVATION IN EUROPEAN SEAS

Deliverable D4.1

Report on the analysis of existing policies and
institutions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of today's most pressing challenges is to safeguard the loss of ecosystem biodiversity and functioning, while simultaneously allowing for their exploitation by those who depend on their services, goods and benefits. In Europe, Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) is the main governance process to ideally integrate sustainability and exploitation. This requires tools and knowledge to align MSP and Marine Protected Area (MPA) designation processes. However, the degree to which these management approaches have been successfully aligned and integrated is debated. The purpose of this Deliverable, Deliverable 4.1 (D4.1), is to report on the existing policies and institutions associated with MSP and MPAs in MarinePlan's eight European Planning Sites, enabling an analysis of how marine governance is being operationalised and a demonstration of the key trends that are emerging across the regions. This Deliverable will provide vital information to guide how MarinePlan co-develops with stakeholders a Decision Support System (DSS) for Ecosystem-Based Maritime Spatial Planning (EB-MSP). Additionally, it will combine with later tasks in Work Package 4 of the MarinePlan project to inform the development of best practice guidance regarding the enhancement of the effectiveness of spatial conservation and restoration measures for marine biodiversity in European Seas.

D4.1 is associated with MarinePlan Task 4.1. As part of Work Package 4, Task 4.1 entails conducting an institutional and policy audit of MPA and MSP processes within each Planning Site. This task also assesses the transboundary links between Planning Sites. Using an established approach to developing stakeholder typologies, the audit identifies and maps the various institutions, policies, and stakeholders involved in MPA and MSP processes. The audit was led by Queen's University Belfast (QUB) and was conducted through detailed documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews with key marine managers within each Planning Site. Documents collated for analysis focused on material produced by governments and included, for example, relevant MSP plans and conservation policies. Key interviewees included marine planners, policy decision-makers, and those responsible for the implementation of European Union (EU) environmental policies and conservation measures. Horrendogram and organogram figures were compiled by each Planning Site to demonstrate the legislative and organisational context of the regions. Thematic analysis was conducted on both the documents and interview transcripts, producing a stakeholder typology for each planning area. These findings identified how organisations and actors participate in current MPA and MSP governance arrangements, and the degree of integration between MPA and MSP processes.

This report provides insight into the Planning Site's institutional settings, clarifying key characteristics and management challenges. Organograms are used to explain the organisational context of each site, denoting what actors are engaged in the institutional management of the regions. Horrendograms are used to clarify the legislative and policy context of each site, exemplifying the complexity of marine governance in the regions. Information is also revealed on how stakeholder participation is operationalised in each of the Planning Site areas. This includes insight into how actors are involved in consultation processes, who are the most influential stakeholders and how they exert their influence. This involves reference to both formal consultation processes and engagement methods beyond consultation. Furthermore, this report presents an overview of how the effectiveness of current policies is being monitored and reviewed in each of the Planning Sites. This includes reference to how evaluation processes are conducted, what this suggests about the adaptive capacity of policy-makers, and whether previous outcomes have informed change. Information is also presented on solutions that have been utilised to respond to emergent challenges in some of the sites.

D4.1 REPORT ON THE ANALYSIS OF EXISTING POLICIES AND INSTITUTIONS

The findings of this report will directly inform the remaining tasks in Work Package 4, as well as providing vital information regarding the governance and policy landscapes of each Planning Site that will contribute to other objectives within the MarinePlan project. The second task of Work Package 4, Task 4.2, will build on the findings presented in this report by exploring how non-government stakeholders are influencing the governance frameworks of each Planning Site. Elements of D4.1 will be used to guide how Task 4.2 assesses the adaptive capacity of existing governance regimes and examines how knowledge is used to inform conservation measures and MSP processes. Furthermore, the findings presented in D4.1 regarding co-development within governance processes will contribute significant insight that will complement other MarinePlan tasks. By demonstrating how co-development varies across institutional contexts, the policy recommendations and solutions proposed by MarinePlan can be tailored to match the individual conditions of each Planning Site. Thus, D4.1 represents not only a valuable audit of existing policies and institutions across multiple European regions, but also a vital resource that will help to inform the development of MarinePlan's practical outputs.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Managing the marine environment to protect its ecological function and sustainability is carried out using a complexity of governance strategies. Governance is used to include legislation, policy, politics, administration and the interplay among them (Boyes & Elliott, 2014). Countries are bound by both internal regional and national policies, laws and agreements, and external regional agreements and laws by being signatories to global initiatives such as the UN Convention of the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). Within the EU, many thematic initiatives have been developed and implemented by Member States to ensure integration between the management of regional seas, spatial planning to ensure human activities are managed sustainably to achieve ecological, economic, and social objectives, protection of vulnerable marine habitats, encouraging cross border cooperation, and the need for integrated marine governance in EU Member States. Particular attention must be taken to accomplish the goals of the Directive 2014/89/EU establishing a framework for MSP.

It is common in most countries that the plethora of marine activities are managed by numerous statutory and competent authorities, departments and administrative agencies (Boyes & Elliott, 2015). These bodies are bound by national and international law to protect and manage the marine area through International or European initiatives, such as MSP, and the protection of important conservation features through networks of protected areas. In most countries, there is no single government department or agency which manages and coordinates the management of the marine environment, and usually different economic sectors (e.g., fisheries, energy, and transport) are all managed under different ministries. Many countries have multiple government departments or agencies with differing priorities which can lead to overlapping jurisdictions, duties and competencies and in some cases gaps in management (Elliott et al., 2022).

Marine management can be regarded as a pyramid moving from the local to the global aspects and vice versa, what may be termed vertical integration, and in which the governance and management of all sectors (e.g., navigation, fisheries) need to be managed together (termed horizontal integration) (Cormier et al., 2022). Each stratum in the pyramid has a differing number of statutory instruments, from the large number of Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) covering each activity in an area, to the few global instruments and agreements. Similarly, the instruments may cover a small area, such as an activity footprint covered by an EIA (Elliott et al., 2020), to the large areas covered by MSPs and the even larger areas covered by regional and global instruments. Accordingly, MSP is required to encompass that horizontal and vertical integration.

The management response footprint elements can then be represented as a site-specific framework for each marine area and maritime state. A legislation figure (horrendogram) showing the existing environmental legislation in the UK (Boyes and Elliott, 2014 – updated following the withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union by Elliott et al., 2022) has been adapted to be used as a template for providing insight into the marine environmental legislation frameworks of the Planning Sites in MarinePlan. This has been successfully used as a tool by other researchers to map marine legislation in several other countries worldwide (Monwar et al., 2020). From the centre moving outwards, the horrendogram maps the vertical governance levels from the international (e.g., United Nations), regional (e.g., EU) and national laws (e.g., country specific implementation) related to marine management which encompasses all activities required to be factored into MSP management. Sectors, as the types of marine use, have also been grouped into segments on the horrendogram based on their management through national legislation (although there are obvious connections made

between different sectors to ensure targets are being met). These groups include ecological protection, fisheries, water quality, flood and risk assessment, MSP, climate change, Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), EIA, shipping and general ocean management.

This Deliverable report, by assessing the legislative and organisational context of the eight MarinePlan Planning Sites, presents an examination of how current governance regimes are operating in practice. Mainly, this is done in an attempt to understand how marine management is being informed, designed and operationalised in different European contexts. The findings presented in D4.1 include a demonstration of the key marine management and governance trends that are emerging across the sites, as well as a review of how adaptive the governance frameworks in each Planning Site are to change. This information represents a valuable reference point for marine governance literature and will be used to tailor the management-related recommendations that are proposed by the MarinePlan project.

1.1 PROJECT OUTLINE

The diversity of terrestrial and marine life is dramatically affected by human interventions including climate change. A compelling growing evidence shows that biodiversity is the basis for ecosystem functions and services and consequently for human benefits depending on those. Thus the importance of ecosystem biodiversity cannot be underestimated calling for an effective management of marine activities and a sustainable use of marine and coastal resources. MSP is the main governance process that ideally balances economic, ecological and socio-cultural goals through the regulation of human uses at sea. With the global and regional conservation and green energy targets ahead, there is an urgent need to define pathways for a better alignment of MSP and strategic conservation planning, hence the operationalisation of an ecosystem approach to MSP. The EU-funded project MarinePlan supports the implementation of ecosystem-based MSP through the development of a decision support system. It will offer guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation and restoration measures during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems.

1.2 AIM OF DELIVERABLE

The aim of D4.1 is to demonstrate and explain the results of an institutional and organisational audit of the MarinePlan Planning Sites. This includes a review of how marine governance is being operationalised in each Planning Site and a demonstration of the key trends that are emerging across the sites. To further realise this aim, D4.1 also presents insight into how adaptive the governance frameworks in each Planning Site are to change. The information included in this report will play a key role in informing the wider MarinePlan project, as well as the following tasks of Work Package 4. Additionally, by illustrating the current state of governance processes across multiple European regions and identifying potential learning lessons, D4.1 has been designed to act as a useful resource for both marine governance researchers and practitioners.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

D4.1 is associated with MarinePlan Task 4.1. As part of Work Package 4, Task 4.1 entails conducting an institutional and policy audit of MPA and MSP processes within each Planning Site. This task also assesses transboundary links between Planning Sites. Using an established approach to developing stakeholder typologies, the audit identifies and maps the various institutions, policies, and stakeholders involved in MPA and MSP processes. The audit was led by QUB and was conducted through detailed documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews with key marine managers within each Planning Site. Documents collated for analysis focused on material produced by governments and included, for example, relevant MSP plans and conservation policies. Key interviewees included marine planners, policy decision-makers, and those responsible for the implementation of EU environmental policies and conservation measures. Horrendogram and organogram figures were compiled by each Planning Site to demonstrate the legislative and organisational context of the regions. Thematic analysis was conducted on both the documents and interview transcripts, producing a stakeholder typology for each planning area. These findings identified how organisations and actors participate in current MPA and MSP governance arrangements, and the degree of integration between MPA and MSP processes. To complete Task 4.1 and ensure that the information required for D4.1 was collected, the Planning Sites were tasked with completing five research objectives:

- 1.** Collect and analyse documents that have governance significance – such as marine plans, conservation policies, and other legislative material – in each Planning Site.
- 2.** Create a horrendogram (or multiple horrendograms for transboundary sites) to document the national legislation and policy that implement protective measures relating to MSP and MPA within each Planning Site.
- 3.** Create an organogram (or multiple organograms for transboundary sites) to document the number of statutory organisations and agencies that have a strategic role in MSP and managing/designating MPAs within each Planning Site.
- 4.** Conduct semi-structured interviews with marine management actors – such as marine planners, policy-makers, and those responsible for EU directives – working with the policy regimes relevant to each Planning Site.
- 5.** Thematically analyse the documents and interview transcripts to produce a review of how marine management is legally and organisationally being implemented in each Planning Site.

1.4 CONTRIBUTORS

Each of MarinePlan's Planning Sites – *Azores; Bay of Biscay; Campania; Celtic Sea; Greek Aegean, Ionian Sea; Southern North Sea; Western Mediterranean Sea, Western Baltic Sea* – have contributed to D4.1. The Planning Sites are central to the MarinePlan project. They will coherently apply the developed tools to derive commonalities, success stories and impediments with regard to the co-development of feasible and realistic planning options to achieve EU Biodiversity strategy targets with the help of an ecosystem approach to EB-MSP. Table 1 (below) indicates the members of the MarinePlan project who have contributed to the development of D4.1.

Contributor name	Affiliation	Role	Planning Site
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Table 1. Names and roles of contributors to D4.1.

1.5 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

The following section ([section 2](#)) explains the methodological framework that guided the research conducted to inform this report. This includes a discussion of the research design that was created, the data collection and analysis methods that were used, and the ethical factors that were considered prior to initiating the research. [Section 3](#) then introduces information regarding the existing policies and institutions of each Planning Site. Sub-sections reveal insight into the legislative and organisational context of the sites ([section 3.1](#)), the major issues affecting the MSP and MPA policy processes in operation ([section 3.2](#)), an assessment of participation frameworks and stakeholder influence ([section 3.3](#)), and an exploration of how the governance regimes in each Planning Site are demonstrating reflexivity and adaptive capacity ([section 3.4](#)). Following this, [Section 4](#) provides some comparative considerations and final remarks. [Section 5](#) then concludes D4.1 by outlining the next steps that this report will inform.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section explains the methodological framework that was created to enable Planning Sites to complete the research objectives associated with Task 4.1. Due to the various research objectives of the Task, a range of research methods were required to be utilised to ensure that the task was completed. These methods, as well as the larger research design that are a part of, are explained in the following sub-sections. The ethical considerations that were factored into this study, as well as information on the ethical approval that was granted to enable the operationalisation of the Task, are noted at the end of this section.

2.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

A workbook for Task 4.1 was designed to guide Planning Sites on how to collect and analyse the relevant information for D4.1. This included information on how the Planning Sites were to graphically map the legislative and organisational information on 'horrendogram' and 'organogram' figures. Guidance was also provided to assist Planning Sites to conduct a documentary analysis of legislative material relevant to their region. Such documents involved material produced by governments, as well as relevant MSP plans and conservation policies. Additionally, the workbook clarified how Planning Sites would be required to carry out semi-structured interviews with key marine managers, such as marine planners, policy-makers and those responsible for the implementation of EU environmental policies and conservation measures. Thematic analysis was then proposed as an analytical method to be conducted on the documents and interview transcripts, enabling the development of a stakeholder typology for each Planning Site. The typology provides important information on how participation processes are designed and implemented in current MPA and MSP governance arrangements, as well as revealing insight into the varying degrees of influence that stakeholders possess and exert within each of the Planning Site regions. Beyond this, thematic analysis enabled Planning Site researchers to critically evaluate the adaptive capacity of current governance regimes and their apparent capacity to tackle future challenges and threats.

2.2 DATA COLLECTION

The documents that Planning Sites collected and analysed included material produced by governments, as well as relevant MSP plans and conservation policies. The objective for Planning Sites was to analyse these documents in an attempt to reveal insight into the core objectives that are listed, how targets are to be achieved, and how participation processes are operationalised. This method of collection and analysis required a critical interpretation of discourse. As an example, the Celtic Sea Planning Site identified several documents that are central to how marine governance is framed and implemented in Ireland. This includes the Maritime Area Planning Act 2021 (passed by the Irish government in 2021), a 2020 government report titled 'Expanding Ireland's Marine Protected Network' (produced by the Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, on behalf of the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage), a revised version of Ireland's Marine Strategy Directive 2008/56/EC (prepared by the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage in 2022), and Project Ireland 2040 National Marine Planning Framework (prepared by the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage). These documents were reviewed, with key points and themes being noted. The documentary reviews were designed as the first research objective for Planning Sites to complete so that the process could inform how other actions within Task 4.1 were to be completed.

For instance, information from the reviews helped researchers to identify some of the legislation and policies that should be listed on the horrendogram figures, as well as facilitating indications of the organisations and departments that could be contacted to source potential interviewees.

The purpose of tasking Planning Sites with creating horrendogram figures was to identify the relevant national legislation and policy that implement protective measures relating to MSP and MPA in their respective regions. The figures help to reveal insight into the varying levels of legislative complexity that Planning Sites face. The guidance provided to Planning Sites on how to construct horrendograms was based on the original work of Boyes and Elliott (2014) and subsequent revisions (Elliott et al., 2022). Horrendograms have been created for each Planning Site, with some transboundary regions producing multiple figures to account for the different nations that fall within their site. The purpose of creating organogram figures was to identify and characterise the number of statutory organisations and agencies that have a strategic role in MSP and managing and designating MPAs within the Planning Site areas. Organograms help to exemplify how a country has multiple government departments with marine competencies, not only the more obvious ministries and departments, such as environment and trade, but also defence, foreign affairs, and transport. By compiling the organogram figures and providing analytical commentary, the Planning Sites have generated valuable insight into who the key governance actors are within their region and the role that have in shaping how the marine environment is managed.

Planning Sites were also required to conduct a range of semi-structured interviews with marine planners and policymakers, as well as those responsible for the implementation of EU environmental policies and conservation measures. Inclusion criteria for the interviews focused on recruiting individuals who have a strong knowledge of the MSP and/or MPA processes in the Planning Site areas. It was recommended that between 5-10 interviews should be conducted by each Planning Site. It was advised that the recruitment of participants was done via purposive sampling, with specific individuals being targeted. This was achieved by the use of expert and snowball sampling forms of purposive sampling. Significant care was taken to ensure that the recruitment process was carried out equitably, ensuring that no potential participants were intentionally excluded. Potential interviewees were initially contacted via email and provided with a MarinePlan participant information sheet. Free and informed consent was obtained from all participants before the collection of data from interviews. To achieve this, potential participants were provided with a project information sheet and a consent form. When necessary, material was translated into local languages. The consent information outlined all aspects with regard to a participant's role in the research, how their information will be processed, who will have access to their information, and how they will appear anonymous.

The semi-structured interviews were guided by thematic questions. The created themes focused on perceptions of existing marine governance regimes, participation processes and stakeholder influence, and the adaptive capacity of such regimes. The interviews also posed questions about the issues related to the legislative, economic, sectoral and administrative aspects within each respective Planning Site. By participating in the interviews, the participants provided vital information on the adaptive capacity of existing governance regimes and how they can facilitate more dynamic approaches to the management of MPAs and MSP. Generating insight into these themes is considered a critical step for MarinePlan to develop realistic and implementable policy recommendations. Moreover, the interviews were also designed to help define the stakeholder typology in each Planning Site area. Interview questions assessed the way that marine managers participate in current MPA and MSP governance arrangements; the stakeholders whom they engage with; their perspectives regarding the degree of integration between MPA and MSP processes; and their thoughts about transboundary issues. The stakeholder typology is important for mapping out stakeholders' influence

and interest. The Task 4.1 workbook included a general list of thematic questions that each Planning Site researcher then adapted to their regional context.

2.3 DATA ANALYSIS

For Task 4.1, Planning Sites were prescribed to thematically analyse their collected data. Thematic analysis is the most useful approach to capturing the complexities of meaning within a textual data set (Terry et al., 2017). Specifically, it can help to examine and provide meaning to the experiences, thoughts, or behaviour, identified across a data set. To be completed successfully, it requires involvement and interpretation from the researcher. Thematic analysis is a form of examination that moves beyond counting explicit words or phrases and, instead, focuses on identifying and describing both implicit and explicit ideas within the data (Clarke et al., 2015). It was decided that a deductive thematic analysis was to be conducted of the documents and interview transcripts that were collected by Planning Sites. A deductive approach involves coming to the data with preconceived themes that were expected to be reflected in the data. Three themes were developed – policy process; participation and stakeholder influence; reflexivity and adaptive capacity – based on theory and existing knowledge of marine governance research. These themes were included in a findings report template that was created by QUB and shared with Planning Sites to guide their analysis. The rationale for taking a deductive approach to this analysis was to ensure that there was commonality in the findings produced by each Planning Site. This helped to identify trends and similarities between the Planning Sites. Additionally, by following a deductive approach, it became possible to produce a stakeholder typology for each respective Planning Site. Extracts and quotations (complemented with descriptive commentary) from the collected documents and interview transcripts are used to populate D4.1's findings. The thematic analysis demonstrates how MPAs and MSP processes are functioning within each Planning Site, with key challenges and opportunities highlighted.

2.4 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Throughout the research, it was imperative that the anonymity of individuals and appropriate levels of confidentiality was to be maintained. This was made clear on information sheets that were shared with participants, and participants were explicitly instructed that their identities would be concealed throughout the study. This resulted in interview data being un-attributable to participants. Labels are used in this report when including quotes from interviews. This ensures that information provided by research participants during interviews is not directly attributable to them. For instance, quotes used from the transcriptions of interviews are presented as: *"a marine planner stated"*, *"a member of the policy committee said"*, *"a government policy expert explained"*. This process, which is explained in the consent forms and information sheets that were shared with interviewees, was made clear before the interviews commenced. To ensure the safe storage of data, collected documents and interview transcripts have been held securely on MarinePlan's SharePoint. Access to the SharePoint is restricted through password protection. Hard copies of signed consent forms have been securely stored in locked filing cabinets and are carefully protected at all times. At no point will any other individual or group who is not a co-investigator have access to the information of research participants. If a participant, for whatever reason, desired to end their participation and to have their contribution retracted, it was made clear to them that they have a window of 6-weeks after their interview to overturn their consent form. In such a scenario, none of their information would be attached to the findings of this report. The MarinePlan ethics document (Deliverable 4.4) was designed following the

granting of ethical approval by Queen's University Belfast's Energy and Physical Sciences (EPS) Faculty Research Ethics Committee in December 2022, in accordance with the Proportionate Review process.

3 EXISTING POLICIES AND INSTITUTIONS

This section presents an analysis of the Planning Sites' collected data. To begin, an overview of the institutional and organisational context of each Planning Site is provided. This includes the presentation of organogram and horrendogram figures that visually illustrate the reality of how the marine environment is governed in each region. Following this, three governance-related themes are used to frame the findings that Planning Sites extracted from policy reviews and semi-structured interviews. The themes cover information relating to MSP and MPA policy processes, participation and stakeholder influence, and the reflexivity and adaptive capacity of governance regimes in each region.

3.1 INSTITUTIONAL AND ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT

Azores

The Azores planning site includes the Portuguese Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) around the EU Outermost Region of the Azores. The Azores archipelago is composed of nine volcanic islands, inhabited by about 240 thousand people spreading along a North-West/South-East-trending strip of 600 km long, with the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) separating the islands of Flores and Corvo, to the west, from the remaining island groups. Portugal's marine jurisdiction around the islands encompasses an EEZ of almost 1 million km² of which about 99% is deep sea, and a claimed continental shelf extension that expands Portuguese sovereignty to approximately twice this value. The Azores are characterized by a complex marine seafloor, home to a large number of seamounts, ridges, trenches and abyssal plains. This variety of landscapes supports rich (deep-sea) benthic ecosystems, where coral gardens and sponge grounds are commonly observed. As in most oceanic islands, fishing has always been a key driver of the subsistence and economy of the Azores (Carvalho, 2010). It is typically characterised as being pelagic and deep-sea artisanal and small-scale in nature, with a multi-segmented fleet, targeting multiple species with a wide range of fishing gear and methods (Carvalho et al., 2011). With the absence of a continental shelf and surrounding great depths, modern fishing occurs around the island slopes and the many seamounts present in its vast EEZ (Diogo et al., 2015). The benthic habitats are, therefore, exposed to fishing, climate change and other anthropogenic pressures, which can put their long-term preservation at risk.

There has been a long history of marine conservation in the Azores that started in the 1980s with the establishment of six coastal MPAs and one offshore marine reserve encompassing the Formigas islets and Dollabarot reef, which imposed fishing limitations to promote the sustainable use of marine resources. In the 1990s, the Azores was highly involved in the implementation of many EU-driven initiatives, namely the EU Habitats and Birds Directives that supported the creation of the Natura 2000 network of MPAs. During the 2000s a joint effort between the Regional Government of the Azores and the University of the Azores resulted in eleven applications of sites to be included in the OSPAR network of MPAs: seven within national waters and four outside national jurisdiction but within the limits of the areas proposed for legal continental shelf extension that Portugal submitted to the United Nations Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf. This made Portugal, and particularly the Azores, a pioneer in the protection of marine biodiversity at an international level and a progressive player that helped to progress the ground-breaking OSPAR high seas MPAs process (Lewison et al., 2015). Many of these MPA applications were supported by the presence of priority habitats (cold-

water gardens and reefs, sponge aggregations, hydrothermal vent fields), and species (orange roughly).

The current fishery resource management strategy of the Azores is based on the EU Common Fishery Policy, implemented primarily through Total Allowable Catches (TACs) for various species (e.g., EC Reg. 2340/2002; EC Reg. 2270/2004) and fishing prohibition for deep-water sharks (e.g., EC Reg 2018/2025). Apart from fish quotas, the regional government of the Azores has implemented technical measures over the years, such as minimum landing sizes or weights, minimum mesh sizes, limitation of licences for some specific gears (e.g., trammel nets), area temporal or permanent closures, and bans on the use of specific gear. The impact of fishing activities on benthic ecosystems has been a particular concern in the Azores, and bottom trawling and deep-sea netting are forbidden around the Azores since 2005 (European Council Regulation [EC] No. 1568/2005 of 20 September 2005; Santos et al., 2009b). Further protection of the deep sea throughout the Azores region was added in 2014 by the creation of an extensive fishery management area that encompasses most of the Portuguese extended continental shelf where bottom-trawling is banned, and by setting move-on rules for the incidental capture (bycatch) of corals and sponges (Portaria 114/2014). Also, a 100-mile polygon around the islands limiting fishing to vessels registered in the Azores was created in 2003 (EC Reg. 1954/2003).

Figure 1. Organogram showing the statutory organisation information for Portugal.

Figure 2. Organogram showing the statutory organisation information for the Azores pt. 1.

Figure 3. Organogram showing the statutory organisation information for the Azores pt. 2.

The Azores Autonomous Region of Portugal is subject to a broad suite of international and national policies, laws and agreements controlling many sectors such as fisheries, energy and conservation. Consequently, there are many organizations and administrative bodies responsible for managing marine affairs. The Regional Government holds specific powers conferred by the Portuguese Constitution and the Political and Administrative Statute of the Autonomous Region of the Azores. The current XIII Regional Government of the Azores is led by the Presidency of the Regional Government with the following secretariats: Regional Secretariat for Finance, Planning and Public Administration, Regional Secretariat for Education and Cultural Affairs, Regional Secretariat for Health and Sport, Regional Secretariat for Agriculture and Rural Development, Regional Secretariat for the Sea and Fisheries (SRMP), Regional Secretariat for the Environment and Climate Change, Regional Secretariat for Tourism, Mobility and Infrastructures, Regional Secretariat for Youth, and the Vocational Training and Employment. The SRMP includes the Regional Directorate for Fisheries (DRP) and the Regional Directorate for Maritime Policies (DRPM) and is responsible for the definition and implementation of regional policies in the areas of oceanography, fisheries and aquaculture, enhancement and preservation of the marine environment, as well as other matters related to the sea. As a member of the DRPM explained, their objectives include *“the planning and management of the coastline and marine protected areas, and maritime spatial planning”*. The horrendogram figure below (Figure 4) illustrates how international, national and regional policies, laws and agreements are connected within the Azores Planning Site.

Figure 4. Horrendogram for the Azores, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Bay of Biscay

The Bay of Biscay (BoB) is a transboundary Planning Site, with well-known physiographical boundaries and significant ecological value, located in the temperate North-East Atlantic Ocean, and bordered by France and Spain. The BoB coastline covers the following regions: in France, Aquitaine, Poitou-Charentes, Pays-de-la-Loire, and Brittany, and in Spain, Galicia, Asturias, Cantabria, and Basque Country. The total population in these regions is almost 19 million people (7 million in Spain and 12 million in France) and it equals to 14% of Spain's and 18% of France's population. The surface area of the BoB is about 175,000 km² (59% of the total area in France and 41% of the total area in Spain's Exclusive Economic Zones and a maximum depth of 4,800 m (Borja et al., 2019). From the ecological point of view, BoB has vital seafloor habitats as spawning and feeding grounds for several fish species (e.g., hake, megrim, anchovy, mackerel, etc.) as well as for species of birds (Pascual et al., 2013) and cetaceans (42 species of marine mammals identified in the region representing the 35% of the total in the world) (Borja et al., 2019). The main social activities are shipping (with important commercial harbours, e.g., Nantes-Saint-Nazaire, Bordeaux, Bilbao, Gijon), fishing (both pelagic and demersal, including recreational, artisanal and industrial fishing), tourism, coastal discharges, dredged sediment disposal (Borja et al., 2019), and emerging activities such as renewable energy exploitation and offshore aquaculture.

This transboundary planning site is under the following international conventions, organizations, agreements, and directives: UNCLOS, the CBD, the International Maritime Organization (IMO), Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), OSPAR Convention (OSPAR region IV), Atlantic Strategy, MSPD, MSFD, WFD and Habitat and Bird Directives (HBD). The BoB and the Iberian coast represent 18.1% of the OSPAR region IV. According to Alloncle et al., (2019), the OSPAR region IV covers around 530.000 km² and contains a network of 349 MPAs, covering 94, 500 km². This is comfortably above the 10% target set in 2010 in the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2010-2020.

Legislative baseline or existing conditions of each of the examined countries were summarised and displayed in their respective horrendograms/organograms. Most of the information was compiled from several Ministries websites in both countries. Both countries have signed and agreed to uphold the same international conventions, laws and/or commitments. In addition, they support common international bodies dedicated to protecting the marine environment, fulfilling the European Commission's Directives and Strategies. Most of the European Directives and Strategies (i.e., MSFD, MSPD) were incorporated into national Laws, Royal Decrees and National Maritime Strategies in both countries. The first difference between these countries is observed in the proposal of an EBSA located in the south of the BoB (bounded by the parallels 43° 25'N and 45° 00'N, and meridians 2° 10'W and 7° 00'W)¹ which includes waters only under Spanish jurisdictions. However, from an ecological point of view, it should be assessed the possibility of extending the geographic limits to also include waters under French jurisdiction.

The following organograms are for both Spain and France despite the institutional landscape for the management of the transboundary planning site. The statutory authorities and organisations involved are depicted according to their administrative hierarchy and their main roles concerning the planning site are briefly described in the organogram. Horrendograms of the BoB Planning Site have also been assembled, detailing the legislative documents relevant to MSP in the Spanish and French parts of the region.

¹ <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/8801/0a69/d1576e45e285306d8c24ec26/template-6-cantabrian-sea-southern-bay-of-biscay-en.pdf> accessed in 21/07/2023.

Figure 5. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Bay of Biscay, showing the statutory organisation information for Spain.

Figure 6. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Bay of Biscay, showing the statutory organisation information for France.

Figure 7. Horrendogram for the Bay of Biscay, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in Spain (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Figure 8. Horrendogram for the Bay of Biscay, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in France (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Campania

In the Mediterranean Sea, the Campania region (about 450 km coastline) along the western coasts of Italy hosts high biodiversity, archaeological remains and geological hazards (i.e., volcanic activities and submarine gas emissions) embedded in areas with high cumulative pressures. About half of the coastline is rocky with very high population density in the Gulf of Naples. The continental shelf is narrow and along the slope, there are three main canyon systems (Dohrn, Cuma, Magnaghi) and relevant vulnerable marine ecosystems (VME, e.g. white corals). A total of 17.1% of the continental shelf is protected through a network of 4 MPAs, 1 Marine Park, 1 Marine Archeological Park, 6 Natura 2000 sites, and 3 fishing restricted areas (ZTB+FRAs). The blue economy of the region is mainly linked to tourism with 11 million tourists in 2021, maritime traffic and shipbuilding, and recreational boating. Fisheries have relevant socio-economic and cultural implications with a fleet of 1088 boats mostly using artisanal fishing gear. Aquaculture is concentrated in the Gulf of Naples with several mussel farms. There is also a fish farm in the South sector of the area (Cilento coasts). A national MSP following the 'Operational guidelines for the preparation of MSP in Italian waters drafted in Jan 2020 (DPCM 1/12/2017)' has been recently implemented but not yet formally endorsed. Conflicts among competing users are expected to increase with the growing use of maritime space. The main objectives for this Planning Site within MarinePlan are the followings 1): assessing the effectiveness of present protection schemes in the region by nationally designed MPAs, Natura 2000 Sites and Fishery Restricted Areas, considering EBSA criteria; 2): identifying additional protection and restoration priorities to revise and expand present conservation measures and achieve EU Biodiversity targets in a human dominated seascape; 3) exploring the trade-offs among EB-MSP planning options with different data resolution; 4) including the consideration of connectivity to build present and future scenarios of protection and restoration. All steps will include the participation of stakeholders at a local scale such as MPAs Directors (Regno di Nettuno, Punta Campanella, Costa infreschi e Castellabate), NGOs (Marevivo, WWF, Lega Ambiente), fishing industry (Federpesca, Coldiretti), and also the regional / national authorities responsible for the MSP, MSFD and MPA designations and fisheries management (GFCM, EU Dg Mare). The planning process will take advantage of ongoing EU projects such as Interreg MED AMARe PLUS and FISHMPABLUE and the EASME project AFRIMED.

The current state of internal legislation on the management of the sea and the protection of the marine environment is very complex and requires a reconstructive effort to understand important aspects, such as the extent of the protection effectively guaranteed by Italy to its natural marine resources. Both the horrendogram and the organogram reflect the hierarchical complexity of the policies applied to the management of the marine environment in Italy and more specifically in the Campania Region. The national policy goal for the protection of marine biodiversity is defined within the National Strategy for Biodiversity 2030 which is foreseen to create a coherent network of MPAs. In this regard the main objectives are the following: 1) to legally protect at least 30% of the EU's land area and 30% of its seas and integrate ecological corridors into a genuine trans-European nature network; 2) strictly protect at least one-third of the EU's protected areas (both on land and at sea), including all primary and old growth forests still existing on its territory; iii) effectively manage all protected areas, defining clear conservation objectives and measures and subjecting them to adequate monitoring. An Italian organogram can be viewed on the page below. A Horrendogram of the Campania Planning Site has also been assembled, detailing the legislative documents relevant to MSP in the region. This is presented in Figure 10.

Italy is a member of the IMO established following the adoption of the Geneva International Maritime Convention of 1948 and in Italian law international agreements apply (e.g., Barcelona Convention of 1976 for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution, the Additional Protocols to the

Barcelona Convention, and UNCLOS). Italy is a Member State of the EU and, as such, the Directives, Programmes, Action Plans, the Conventions and European policies explain effects, more or less directly in the national legal system. That said, however, the regulatory framework is characterised, at a national level, also by the presence of rules that complete the legal framework and establish specific forms of protection for the Italian marine environment. The governance system is made more complex by the role played by the regional administrations which can implement local policies for specific sectors (e.g., aquaculture development, maritime domain planning, Natura 2000 sites planning, etc.). For these reasons compiling the horrendogram was a very complex task which requires a wider knowledge of the governance/administrative framework. One important aspect relating to the coastal management of the Planning Site is the recent development of a spatial plan for aquaculture (AZA: allocated zones for aquaculture) in the Campania region, that will be integrated within the national MSP. It is also important to mention that the institution of MPAs was a process in which the local municipalities (“comuni costieri”) have played a key role as promoters of their legal implementations. The environmental department of the Campania Region administration was responsible for the identification and management of Natura 2000 sites as well as of the coastal ZTB (Zona di Tutela Biologica: Special Protected Area) of Banco di S. Croce. The Italian administrative landscape concerning the management of the sea is under the responsibility of 8 different Ministries with different competencies as shown in the organogram. The development of the MSP is led by the Ministry of Infrastructures and Transports. MPA implementations is under the responsibility of the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE).

Figure 9. Organogram for the Campania Planning Site, showing the statutory organisation information for Italy.

Figure 10. Horrendogram for Campania, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in Italy (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Celtic Sea

The Celtic Sea, part of the Atlantic Ocean, is situated off the Southern coast of Ireland. It is bordered by Saint George's Channel to the east and includes other limits such as the English Channel, the Bristol Channel, and the BoB (Hervann et al., 2020). The area where the Planning Site is located encompasses basin countries like Ireland, England, Wales, and France, making it a transboundary sea. However, the Celtic Sea Planning Site itself is not transboundary in terms of spatial delimitation. It is a national planning site that will analyse marine governance within the framework of Irish legislation, derived from both regional and international legal and policy frameworks (Government of Ireland, 2023). This area is highly productive, supporting a diverse marine environment and various socio-economic activities, particularly fishing, shipping, and recreational pursuits. It has also recently been identified as a key area for the development of emerging Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE).

In 2021, Ireland established a national MSP, known as the National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF), in accordance with the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive 2014/89/EU (Government of Ireland, 2023). This Framework constitutes environmental, economic, and social objectives to ensure the sustainable future of Ireland's maritime area. It is complemented by The Maritime Area Planning (MAP) Act of 2021, designed to regulate activities and developments in the maritime area. Presently, the only designated marine protected sites in Ireland are declared under the EU Birds (Council 79/409/EEC) and Habitats (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) Directives, labelled as Special Protected Areas (SPAs) and Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) respectively. These SPAs and SACs cover 8% of Ireland's Exclusive Economic Zone, with less than 1% occurring in the Planning Site (NPWS, 2023). However, in December 2022, the General Scheme of the Bill for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) was approved by the Irish government. The proposed legislation is expected to progress into law by the end of the first quarter of 2024².

The MPA legislation will establish a legal framework for identifying, designating, monitoring, and managing MPAs, providing support to the MAP Act of 2021 as well as existing biodiversity protection legislation. The delay in finalizing this law will pose a challenge for the government in achieving the goal of protecting 30% of the EEZ by 2030, in alignment with the Global Biodiversity Framework. Balancing sustainable exploitation with marine conservation measures remains a significant challenge, which the Planning Site study aims to address. Efforts are underway to develop a more holistic, Ecosystem-Based approach (O'Higgins et al., 2019).

Ireland has established a comprehensive legal framework for managing maritime activities. This framework extends from regional and international levels down to the national level, indicating a vertical legal structure. It encompasses legislation pertaining to Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), environmental protection, and economic development within the maritime sector. The Department of Housing, Local Government, and Heritage (DHLGH) takes the lead in Ireland's establishment of MSP and MPA policies. They work in consultation with other government departments, including the Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine (DAFM), which oversees fisheries and seafood, and the Department of Environment, Climate, and Communications (DECC), responsible for climate change and offshore energy development. In total, seven government departments share marine responsibilities, with a total of 92 distinct marine agencies. At times, this multiplicity can lead to challenges, as each department may have conflicting concerns.

² <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/2fd71-general-scheme-of-marine-protected-areas-bill-2022/> Accessed on 29/09/2023.

Most international and EU policies pertaining to marine management have been integrated into national law. However, Ireland has yet to designate Other Effective Areas of Conservation Measures (OECMs) and EBSAs. One of the objectives of this Planning Site will be to identify EBSAs in the Celtic Sea Planning Site and incorporate them into Ecosystem-Based MSP. While much legislation has been adopted into national law, it can sometimes be unclear how effectively these policies are implemented, managed, and monitored at the national level. Further analysis could reveal areas for improvement in marine management governance. Given the evolving legal landscape in Ireland, the introduction of new legislation may necessitate updates to the institutional framework, as depicted in the current organogram and horrendogram. Ensuring consistency and coherence in the application of these laws and policies remains a challenge, especially in reconciling different legal frameworks at the national, regional, and international levels.

In total, the institutional landscape in Ireland, particularly within the Celtic Sea Planning Site, is shaped by a combination of national, regional, and international legal and policy frameworks. This landscape is dynamic, reflecting ongoing efforts to balance economic exploitation with marine conservation measures. Mapping this landscape involves navigating complex legal relationships and understanding the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders, which can be intricate and interconnected. The unique characteristics of the wider Celtic Sea beyond the spatial boundary of the Planning Site add an additional layer of complexity, particularly in managing transboundary resources. Organogram and horrendogram figures of the Celtic Sea region have also been assembled, detailing the organisational and legislative landscape relevant to Ireland. These can be viewed on the pages below.

Figure 11. Organogram for the Celtic Sea Planning Site, showing the statutory organisation information for Ireland.

Figure 12. Horrendogram for the Celtic Sea, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in Ireland (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas

The Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site constitutes a national Planning Site that adheres to the overall policy framework of Greece. The fundamental legislative process for declaring protected areas in Greece includes the elaboration of a Special Environmental Study and a Management Plan for each Protected Area. The Special Environmental Studies primarily focus on designating protected areas, defining zones within them, and considering the need for regional zoning and ecological corridors. They also propose regulations, measures, and actions to preserve the unique features of each protected area. The Management Plans prioritize management actions, interventions, and measures required to effectively maintain and safeguard the protected object within these areas. The integration of the EU MSP Directive into Greek policy includes establishing a National Maritime Spatial Strategy and Maritime Spatial Frameworks. The Strategy outlines policy principles for sustainable maritime development, managing interactions between coastal and maritime areas, and coordinating policies with spatial implications. Maritime Spatial Frameworks are comprehensive documents providing guidance for spatial development and organization within marine areas and represent the initial applied effort for MSP in the Planning Site.

Both the development of MSP and MPA policies are led by the Ministry of the Environment and Energy in collaboration with other national authorities, with active engagement of external stakeholders. Despite the long-standing institutionalization of the policy development process for both sectors, Greece has not fulfilled its obligations in either of them, leading to significant management challenges for the Planning Site. A significant number of legislative documents related to the integration of EU policies into national planning have been identified. Both the Horrendogram and the Organogram indicate regular revisions of legislation and the responsibilities assigned to relevant Departments. While some regulations have been adopted in the past, they lack renewal and clear references in written documents regarding the responsible monitoring agency. Conversely, certain regulations undergo frequent updates. In many cases, responsibilities are distributed among multiple departments, and with proper collaboration, this arrangement can foster effective management. The main Directorates responsible for managing MPAs and operating MSP are primarily located within the Ministry of Environment and Energy. Additionally, key partners include the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Insular Policy and the Ministry of Rural Development and Food. While it appears that other Ministries and bodies may have overlapping jurisdictions, their cooperation is often limited to specific issues, leading to doubts about the practical implementation of this collaboration and the extent of substantial co-formation in management policies and implementation strategies.

Figure 13. Organogram for the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site (pt. 1), showing the statutory organisation information for Greece.

Figure 14. Organogram for the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site (pt. 2), showing the statutory organisation information for Greece.

Figure 15. Organogram for the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site (pt. 3), showing the statutory organisation information for Greece.

A Horrendogram was compiled aiming to identify and link international, regional, European, and national legislation directly related to MSP and MPAs in Greece. The Greek state has effectively incorporated most of the European regulations into its national policy. Although this is an encouraging finding, suggesting quick reflexes in policy integration, the overall analysis indicates that mere legislative compliance does not guarantee implementation. While the Horrendogram presents a comprehensive overview of the institutional framework of the Planning Site, further examination may reveal significant policy gaps. The EU Habitats Directive stands out as the most closely monitored legislative document over time. Although Greece has not yet identified any OECSs (Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures) or officially ratified EBSAs (Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas), the country has recently taken a significant step by recognizing Key Biodiversity Areas in its laws and policies, offering an alternative protection scheme that could complement these approaches. The horrendogram is presented on the page below.

Figure 16. Horrendogram for the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in Greece (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Southern North Sea

The Southern North Sea (SNS) case study encompasses four countries: Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany and part of England. As part of the North Sea, it is an intensively used and industrialized area. All the included countries have a Maritime Spatial Plan that is implemented and legally binding. The English example differs in the sense that there is not actual map, but a set of written rules regarding what can and cannot happen in their part of the North Sea, and what activity has priority over the other ones. All three other countries have maps, communicated to the public, with zones dedicated to the activities taking place in it. The major industrial sectors identified for the area are the following: fishing, shipping, oil/gas extraction, sand extraction, offshore windfarms and aquaculture. Not all sectors concern each country. For example, whilst there is no oil or gas extraction in Belgium, this is prominent in England. Similarly, there is no aquaculture in English waters, although that sector is well-developed in the Netherlands. The following map displays the SNS case study with some activities represented.

The accompanying organogram figures provide information on the statutory landscape of each Planning Site in the SNS. As they demonstrate, the landscape is fragmented. Policies often overlap both at European and regional levels. There is also evidence of different levels of implementation in federal states and an overall difficulty in comprehending how these different policies are integrated with each other. Horrendograms per country of the SNS Planning Site have also been assembled, detailing the legislative documents relevant to MSP in the region. These can be viewed on the following pages.

Figure 17. Map showing the human activities taking place in the Southern North Sea Planning Site.

The implementation of MSP across the English portion of the SNS case study area is delivered through the joint action of several of the UK Government's (statutory) Executive Non-Departmental Public Bodies (ENDPBs) that are positioned within the Government's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA). Whilst ultimately it is the UK Government's Secretary of State who holds responsibility for developing Marine Plans in English inshore and offshore regions, this responsibility is discharged primarily through the actions of the Marine Management Organisation (MMO).

The MMO has a statutory responsibility both for marine planning (and licensing) in English waters and for the development of marine plans (*de facto* MSP) covering the English marine area. Support in the delivery of these activities is provided by two further ENDPBs: Natural England (NE), which has statutory responsibilities for the provision of strategic advice to government on marine conservation and seascape issues in England's territorial waters out to 12nm, as well as for regulatory advice to industry; and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC), which has its own statutory responsibilities for nature conservation in the offshore marine environment (extending from the territorial (12nm) limit out to the UK Continental Shelf). As required, additional advice to support the MMO's planning process may be provided by other ENDPBs such as the Environment Agency (EA) or the Sea Fish Industry Authority (SFIA). The key relevant responsibilities of all these Public Bodies are summarised in Figure 10. In addition, further support to the planning process comes from the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture (CEFAS) which can be called upon to provide advice regarding marine planning and environmental licensing across all UK territorial waters.

Figure 18. Organogram of England showing national bodies linked to MSP, and their relationship with each other.

Figure 19. Focus on the English Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA).

Figure 20. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Southern North Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for Belgium.

In Belgium, MSP is a federal competency and falls under the responsibility of the Ministry of the North Sea (North Sea Cabinet). The practical implementation and management of the plan are coordinated by the Marine Environment Service within that ministry. The other bodies in the organogram participate in the MSP process through advisory and consultation processes. In the Netherlands, legislation for MSP is part of the National Water Act. The competent authority for MSP is the Interdepartmental Directors' Consultative Body North Sea, led by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, which dictates a National Water Plan to be drafted every six years. The current act states that EB-MSP will build on the Marine Strategy and a program of measures to ensure good environmental status of the sea. Additionally, the National Water Plan ensures taking into account all relevant Land-Sea Interactions. For various sectoral interests, specific legislation is in place. For instance, the Electricity Law regulating offshore renewable electricity to be landed, or the Common Fisheries Policy of the EU for sustainable fisheries. These aspects are illustrated in the Dutch horrendogram (Figure 26).

Figure 21. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Southern North Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for the Netherlands.

In Germany, the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, BSH) is responsible for MSP. It provides the technical expertise and the marine spatial plan coordinating and implementing MSP activities. The BSH collaborates closely with the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (Bundesamt für Naturschutz, BfN), which provides expertise and guidance on environmental and conservation aspects such as MPAs. All other bodies mentioned in the

organogram are linked to MSP through consultation, coordination or execution/enforcement of MSP actions.

Figure 22. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Southern North Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for the German part of the site.

Several horrendogram figures have been created to demonstrate the legislative landscape of each of the SNS Planning Site nations. This includes details of the international, European and national legislation that gives protection to the marine environment in the UK, Belgium, the Netherlands and Germany. These are included on the pages below.

Figure 24. Horrendogram for the Southern North Sea, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in Belgium (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Figure 26. Horrendogram for the Southern North Sea, showing international, European and national legislation, giving protection to the marine environment in the Netherlands (after Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Western Mediterranean Sea

The Western Mediterranean Sea Planning Site has an area of about 846,000 km², and it includes EU and non-EU countries (Europe and North Africa). This region is subjected to intense human pressures, including high fishing of commercial species and large discarding and by-catch rates of non-commercial and vulnerable species, as well as climate change effects such as intense sea warming (including marine heatwaves), ocean acidification and changes in primary production. In addition, habitat degradation, pollution and the introduction of invasive species (e.g., blue crab) are challenging the management of coastal and marine resources. National plans are still in their first steps in some countries and they do not exist yet in other ones. There is not a regional MSP structure but there are some international sectorial marine planning initiatives. Furthermore, the establishment of Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) permanent or seasonal, and the implementation of larger MPAs to conserve and restore VME and Essential Fish Habitats (EFH), achieving 30% protection for 2030 is being discussed.

In this Planning Site, the key objectives are to provide strategic data-driven analysis at the Western Mediterranean basin regional scale, following a transnational and regional approach. The analysis proposed here is addressed considering this zoom-out strategy based on the ecosystem-based approach in the Western Mediterranean basin. The main objectives for the Western Mediterranean Planning Site are transboundary scenarios on MSP and coherent and robust conservation planning to meet 2030-30%-10% targets at the regional level; and the assessment of cumulative human pressures on EBSAs and the risk for ecosystem services at the regional level. The European Commission, National European Ministries and General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) are the key-player stakeholders because they may have the highest influence and interest related to the regional outputs of this Planning Site in the framework of the MarinePlan project.

In the Western Mediterranean Sea Planning Site, the legislation and institutions at a regional level have been analysed, with some additional information regarding the National level also assessed. For more details, National legislation and institutions can be checked through the GPSAzores Report (Monwar et al., 2020) and also by the analyses conducted by the BoB (Spain and France) and by Campania Planning Sites in the framework of the MarinePlan project. Results reported here help to assess the complexity level of legislation regarding marine ecosystems but also how the international institutions are committed to protecting marine ecosystems in this region. In terms of institutions, they show that there are two major organisations at a regional level: The United Nations and the European Commission. In both cases, sub-bodies are in charge of different topics such as environment, climate change, and fisheries, among others. In general, except for the Directorate General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE), these institutions have different objectives that can be linked to specific roles in MSP or MPAs processes through direct or indirect actions.

In the Western Mediterranean Sea Planning Site, there are two major organisations. These are: The United Nations and the European Commission. In terms of subcategory bodies, results show that in the United Nations, there are more internal bodies related to the protection of marine ecosystems compared to the European Commission. In general, all bodies have different aims with an important role in MSP and/or MPAs processes having different indirect and direct actions. Overall, the conclusion is that the international and European institutions have a high level of commitment concerning marine ecosystem protection and MSP. Figure 27, an Organogram of the Western Mediterranean Sea basin, demonstrates this information.

Figure 27. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Western Mediterranean Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for the Western Mediterranean Sea basin. To view this figure in greater definition, [click here](#).

All legislation at international, regional and European levels has been included in the Horrendogram (Figure 28). It also includes how European countries have translated each Directive at the National Level (Enabling/Primary Legislation boxes) and how it is implemented in general terms (Legislative protection afforded boxes). It is important to mention the complexity and fragmentation of the legislation regarding all the issues that MSP has to consider and the no unification that encompasses the protection of marine ecosystems, nor is there a general marine law that is above the rest of the laws. The UNCLOS is a unique law regarding marine issues but it is too general and there are no specificities in terms of MSP or MPAs processes.

Western Baltic Sea

The Western Baltic Sea is a transition area between the fully marine areas bordering the North Sea and the brackish parts of the Baltic Sea. Overfishing and climate change have recently caused collapses of the two major fisheries targets cod and herring, threatening traditional fisheries and the communities they rely on. Fisheries are furthermore restricted by marine space requirements for renewable energy production and marine biodiversity protection through Natura 2000 sites. Currently, sites fitting the 2030-30%-10% EB-MSP scenarios are discussed nationally, but knowledge gaps exist on (i) the efficiency of existing Natura 2000 and other sites to protect local biodiversity hotspots and the life-history connectivity of the important commercial fish species, (ii) the extent of the limitations that protected areas put on commercial fisheries economic viability, and (iii) the interference of e.g. offshore wind farms or gravel extraction with biodiversity hotspots and traditional fishing grounds. The Western Baltic Planning Site is a transboundary area, with Denmark, Germany and to a limited extent Sweden surrounding the study site. The eastern part of the Øresund as well as national waters along the Swedish south coast are under Swedish jurisdiction and not covered in this project. Horrendograms per country of the Western Baltic Sea Planning Site have been assembled, detailing the legislative documents relevant to MSP in both Denmark and the German component of this region (Figures 31 and 32).

As in the SNS, in Germany, the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, BSH) is responsible for MSP. It provides the technical expertise and the marine spatial plan coordinating and implementing MSP activities. The BSH collaborates closely with the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (Bundesamt für Naturschutz, BfN), which provides expertise and guidance on environmental and conservation aspects such as MPAs. All other bodies mentioned in the organogram are linked to MSP through consultation, coordination or execution/enforcement of MSP actions. In Denmark, MSP is tightly coordinated between the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry for Industry, Business and Financial Affairs. These authorities stand for the 'Danish Marine Plan' setting and implementing MSP activities. The ministries include the Danish Nature Agency and the Danish Maritime Authority. The other bodies mentioned in the organogram are linked to MSP through consultation or coordination of MSP actions, mainly with a focus on scientific advice for prospective closed areas.

Figure 29. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Western Baltic Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for Denmark.

Figure 30. Organogram for the transboundary Planning Site of the Western Baltic Sea, showing the statutory organisation information for the German part of the site.

3.2 POLICY PROCESS

This sub-section demonstrates the organisation of the policy processes that underpin marine governance in each of the Planning Site areas. In doing so, it illustrates what policies are being created, what their objectives are, how they are being informed, and how they consider transboundary issues. Information is revealed regarding the networks and structures that policy-makers participate in to achieve their policy goals. Reference is also made to the emergent challenges that hinder MSP and MPA integration, as well as consideration of how these have been responded to in different contexts.

Azores

The regional policies for the governance of the ocean are based on co-management work to promote integrated and sustainable management. This was explained by a government official, who asserted that policy processes are designed to *“align the interests of various political and economic agents and stakeholders”*. It was clarified by the same actor that the regional policies *“rely on the contribution of researchers, fishers and associations of the sector”*. Portugal was one of the first Member States to undertake the MSP process, but the country was missing a specific plan for the Azores archipelago. At the time of its development, MSP in Portugal’s outermost region was the responsibility of the regional government of the Azores. However, In July 2022, the Portuguese Constitutional Court mandated the central government with the exclusive responsibility for the implementation of EU maritime Directives, bypassing regional authorities’ influence over the matter. The Azores MSP process (POEMA) is being led by the DRPM with the support of several co-financed projects such as the MarSP, PLASMAR and, more recently, MSP-OR and PLASMAR+ projects. The situation (or status) plan for Maritime Spatial Planning in the Azores documents, and respective Strategic Environmental Assessment, was produced in 2022 and was presented to interested parties during several moments of consultation, with the objectives, methodologies and key elements of the Plan being widely discussed. The situation plan received a non-binding favourable opinion from the Consultative Committee in July 2023 and is now being submitted to public consultation. At the same time, the Regional Government of the Azores, signed a memorandum of understanding over the “Blue Azores” Program, to promote the conservation and sustainable use of resources, by declaring 30% of the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Azores as marine protected areas of which 15% should be strictly protected. The Blue Azores process was not officially integrated into the MSP process. Due to the diversity of ocean stakeholders and the availability of scientific data, the process for the revision of the MPA network was conducted on the Offshore Network only (areas beyond 6 nm from the coastline).

To provide an example of how marine policy processes operate in the Azores, it is useful to reference the Azores Network of Marine Protected Areas. The network was set up by the regulation ‘Decreto Legislativo Regional nº 15/2007/A’ with the overall objective to protect and restore biodiversity and habitats, particularly in the deep sea, that have been negatively affected by human activities or might be negatively affected in the future. The Azores Network of Marine Protected Areas includes the Island Natural Park within the territorial waters (12nm) and the Azores Marine Park beyond territorial waters. The network of protected areas declared in the Azores Marine Park is the main instrument for marine biodiversity conservation in the deep-sea beyond territorial waters (12nm). It is coordinated by the Regional Directorate for Maritime Affairs (DRAM) together with an advisory council. Eleven MPAs were included in the Azores Marine Park in 2011 (DLR n.º 28/2011/A), while the MPA of the

Meteor Submarine Archipelago, seamounts Condor and Princesa Alice and a large area in the Mid Atlantic Ridge southwest of Flores were included in 2016 (DLR n.º 13/2016/A).

An update in 2016 defined in the regulatory decree-law nº 13/2016/A and the 2019 addition of the Luso hydrothermal vent field defined in the Portaria nº 68/2019, the Azores Marine Park is now composed of 16 Marine Protected Areas, covering an area of 135,507 km² both within and partially beyond the Portuguese EEZ. In addition to these areas, the Marine Reserve of the Formigas islets regulated under the Santa Maria Island Natural Park (Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 39/2012/A), is also a relevant MPA for marine biodiversity conservation in the deep-sea. All the areas regulated under this network fall within several IUCN categories (Calado et al., 2011): nature reserves (IUCN I); protected areas for management of particular habitats or species (IUCN IV); and MPAs for resource management (IUCN VI). Broadly speaking, those MPAs can be separated between two categories: the Marine Natural Reserves (IUCN I) that constitute permanent bottom-fishing closures and thus ensure the full protection of the seabed and the demersal species, and the other MPAs where fishing activities are regulated but not prohibited.

The Marine Protected Area of seamount Don João de Castro includes a small Marine Natural Reserve that encompasses shallow (20m) hydrothermal vents (IUCN category I), which in turn are encompassed by a larger Marine Protected Area for resource management (PM11, IUCN Category VI). This seamount is also classified as an EU Natura 2000 site. The hydrothermal vents Menez Gwen (PMA 2) and Lucky Strike (PMA3) are also Nature Reserves and are protected against bottom contact fishing, deep-sea mining, dumping and other activities that may cause harm to the marine environment (IUCN category I; DLR 28/2011/A). The Rainbow vent field is a Nature Reserve located in the continental shelf behind 200nm claimed by Portugal, but it lacks effective protection measures (DLR 28/2011/A). The Menez Hom, Famous, Saldanha, and Amar vent fields, also lack effective protection measures (DLR 13/2016/A). In fact, deep-sea mining exploration activities are not prohibited in PMA13, but they require special permits as it would be necessary for any other area. The Luso hydrothermal vent field is fully protected from fisheries since September 2019 (Portaria 68/2019). However, the regulation does not mention other activities rather than fisheries, and therefore deep-sea mining exploration and scientific research were not subject to specific rules or prohibitions.

As for the seamounts within the network, the Sedlo and the Formigas seamounts are Natural Reserves with fisheries restrictions to all types of gear except epipelagic fishing, deep-sea mining, dumping and other activities that may cause harm to the marine environment (IUCN, Category I), while the Condor and Princesa Alice seamounts are marine protected areas for resource management (IUCN VI). The Condor seamount also benefits from strong protection, as it was closed in 2010 to bottom fishing for research purposes until 2020. The MPA of Princesa Alice seamount protects only the summit of this feature. Offshore seamounts beyond the Azorean EEZ (Altair, Antialtair), MARNA and the Meteor seamount complex are protected for resource management under IUCN category VI, but in practice, they lack effective protective measures. Very few MPAs have been declared to achieve conservation goals related to large megafauna, including seabirds. The exceptions are the Offshore MPAs North of Corvo and North of Faial which were designated as Marine Important Bird Areas (MIBAs) for the protection of the Cory's Shearwater (*Calonectris diomedea*). Despite the significant progress that the Azores has made in regard to MPA development, it appears evident that the majority of MPAs have achieved little success in attaining conservation or restoration objectives. This hints that there is a need to revise the frameworks and policy targets through which the MPA network is intended to function.

Bay of Biscay

For this section, the initial focus will be on the MPA policy process in the BoB. In Spain, MPAs were created by *Law 42/2007 on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity* (Articles 29 and 32). According to this law, the MPAs, and other protected areas in the Spanish marine environment, are part of the Network of MPAs in Spain (RAMPE). Subsequently, *Law 41/2010 for the protection of the marine environment* formally created the RAMPE, regulated and established its objectives and the mechanisms for its designation and management. It also specified the functions that the MITECO will carry out in relation to the RAMPE. According to Law 41/2010, it is the responsibility of the General State Administration to prepare, together with the competent coastal Autonomous Communities, the proposal for the minimum common criteria for the coordinated and coherent management of the RAMPE, which in accordance with article 33.3 of Law 42/2007 must be included in the Master Plan of the RAMPE. Finally, the *Royal Decree 1629/2011* declared the marine space of “El Cachucho”, located in the BoB Planning Site area, as the first MPA in Spain, as a Special Zone of Conservation, and the corresponding conservation measures.

The resolution of November 20th, 2015, of the General Directorate for Sustainability of the Coast and the Sea, establishes that the special protection areas for seabirds of the Natura 2000 Network, located in the BoB Planning Site area, were integrated into the RAMPE: ES0000490, Espacio Marino de la Ría de Mundaka-Cabo de Ogoño; ES0000492, Espacio Marino de los Islotes de Portios-Isla Conejera-Isla de Mouro; ES0000494, Espacio Marino de Cabo Peñas; ES0000496, Espacio Marino de la Costa de Ferrolterra-Valdoviño; ES0000497, Espacio Marino de la Costa da Morte³.

Figure 33. Map of the MPA network in the Bay of Biscay (OSPAR region IV) (modified from Alloncle *et al.*, 2019).

³ (<https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/biodiversidad-marina/espacios-marinos-prottegidos/red-areas-marinas-prottegidas-espana/red-rampe-index.aspx>).

In the context of the EBSA declaration, for the unification of criteria and continuity/cross-border cooperation, some contact/work groups were created that were going to meet at the last COP 27. However, these meetings were finally postponed due to other agenda priorities.

In France, the national strategy for the creation and management of MPAs dates from 2012. Then, France transposed the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020 and its 20 Aichi Targets into its national biodiversity strategy (2011-2020), adopting the national strategy for the creation and management of MPAs (2012-2020). The National Strategy for Protected Areas 2030, for the period 2020-2030, deals with the reinforcement and extension of the network, but also with qualitative management issues common to all types of protected areas or with mitigation and adaptation to climate change. The French Biodiversity Agency (FBA) is the branch of the Ministry of Ecological Transition which leads the development and implementation of this strategy. The FBA is involved in the management and coordination of MPAs in France. The FBA contributes to the planning and design of MPAs. It provides guidance and advice on the selection of sites, the establishment of boundaries, and the zoning of different activities within MPAs. FBA's expertise helps to ensure that MPAs are ecologically representative, effectively managed, and contribute to the conservation of marine biodiversity. The FBA provides technical expertise on marine biodiversity and conservation. It conducts research, monitoring, and assessment activities to gather scientific knowledge about marine ecosystems and species within MPAs. The FBA plays a role in raising awareness and outreach in promoting the importance of MPAs for biodiversity conservation. The NBA counts on the scientific and technical support of PatriNat, which ensures the coordination, monitoring, revision and evaluation of MPAs⁴. PatriNat is the French national database on natural heritage. In the context of MPAs, PatriNat provides a centralized and comprehensive database that gathers and manages information related to the country's biodiversity, natural heritage sites, and protected areas, including MPAs.

In Spain, national MSP processes were developed in the normative context of National Marine Strategies for each of the five marine demarcations established by Law 41/2010 Protection of the Marine Environment (transposed from the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive). In this sense, Royal Decree 373/2017 indicates that "This spatial management framework will constitute a common guideline for all marine strategies, in accordance with the provisions of article 4.2.f of the Law on the protection of the marine environment". According to this RD, five MSP plans for each five Spanish marine demarcations. The environmental information in the Spanish MSP includes, among others, the National MPAs. Moreover, one of the main objectives of the national MSP is to guarantee that the plans contemplate the need for an increase of the marine surface protected in marine demarcation and that the activities or uses contemplated in those areas do not compromise their designation as protected areas. The Spanish MSP process contemplates inter-administrative coordination through three collegiate bodies: (i) the Inter-ministerial Commission for Marine Strategies (CIEM) is the collegiate body for coordination between the different Ministerial departments, which was created by Article 22 of Law 41/2010 on the protection of the marine environment. The CIEM celebrates several working groups, one of which is the Working Group on Maritime Space Planning. This group is of a technical nature and brings together the different units of the General Administration of Spain (AGE); (ii) Monitoring Committees for coordination with the Autonomous Communities, there are five Spanish marine demarcations; (iii) the Government's Delegate Commission for Economic Affairs to examine and deliberate on all relevant proposals on matters of sectoral economic content.

⁴ <https://professionnels.ofb.fr/fr/node/650>

The MSP Directive and the Spanish Royal Decree 373/2017 provide the need to cooperate with other Member States to ensure that national MSPs are consistent across countries and between neighbouring countries. In the case of the BoB, cross-border cooperation took place between France and Spain taking part in various community initiatives: Expert Groups on MSP, Marine Spatial Experts Group (MSEG), coordinated by the European Commission. Moreover, both countries participate in the mechanism for assistance to Member States with a platform for the exchange of information and experience (MSP Platform), and the European Maritime Forum (EU Maritime Forum). In Spain, during the consultation of the initial documents of the Strategic Environmental Assessment of the national MSP (January and June 2020), a consultation of interest was carried out with neighbouring Member States (France, Italy and Portugal). In September 2021, an ad-hoc meeting was held with these countries (online format) to present the plans to them and get their feedback, impressions, and comments. Also, informal technical meetings in Marine Subregions with these countries to discuss common marine issues. In these meetings were present the Spanish Oceanographic Institute-IEO, the Spanish Centre for Studies and Experimentation of Public Works-CEDEX and in France, the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer-IFREMER and CEREMA.

In France, the MSP Directive was transposed into French legislation through the entry into force of Art. 123 of Law n° 2016-1087 which defines the documents stratégiques de façade (DSF) ('Sea basin strategic documents') as the main tools through which MSP is implemented. These documents contain two parts: i) Initial assessment and strategic objectives and MSP - vocational map and fact sheets (finalised in September/October 2019); Monitoring mechanism and action plan (finalised in April/May 2022); ii) Initial assessment and strategic objectives and MSP - vocational map and fact sheets (finalised in September/October 2019); Monitoring mechanism and action plan (finalised in April/May 2022). The Secretary of State for the Sea is the national authority responsible for the overall planning of maritime space. Specifically, the Ministry is charged with i) Ensuring the coherence of strategic plans at the national level; ii) Consulting with the National Committee for the Sea and Shorelines (Conseil National de la Mer et des Littoraux), which brings together stakeholders' national representatives; iii) Reporting strategic plans to the European Commission. In turn, the National Committee for the Sea and Shorelines is engaged in the development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the strategy. In France, the Maritime Prefect is one of the authorities that coordinates the sea-basin strategy. The other one is the Coordinator Prefect which is nominated especially for the purpose. REMA conducts research and develops methodologies, tools, and guidelines to support MSP processes. It contributes to an understanding of coastal and marine ecosystems, sustainable maritime development, and integrated coastal zone management. CEREMA in turn carries out capacity building and training programs related to MSP. It works closely with government agencies, regional authorities, research organizations, and stakeholders, to foster collaboration and coordination in MSP. The centre develops tools such as spatial planning software, decision-support systems, and guidelines for assessing environmental impacts, managing maritime activities, and integrating multiple uses of marine space.

Campania

The most important recent development of the policies linked to marine protection in Italy and along the Campania coasts is the development of a national MSP. The MSP Plan was drawn by a technical committee (Legislative Decree 17 October 2016, n.201 – containing the “implementation of directive 2014/89/EU establishing a framework for MSP”) set up at the Competent Authority (Ministry of Infrastructures and Transports), which includes representatives of central and regional (15 Coastal Regions) administrations appointed with D.M. 529 of 13 November 2017 and subsequent

amendments. The Competent Authority (CA) and the Technical Committee availed themselves of the technical-scientific and operational assistance of scientific institutions (i.e. CNR-ISMAR, CORILA and the IUAV University of Venice). The CA has identified three maritime areas of reference, for the preparation of three coordinated Plans, attributable to the three sub-regions referred to in the Marine Strategy (Article 4 of Directive 2008/56/EU): the Adriatic Sea; the Ionian Sea and the central Mediterranean Sea; the western Mediterranean Sea. This latter includes the Campania Region. The Plans will have a duration of 10 years, with the possibility of a mid-term review, or if deemed necessary following the monitoring of the implementation of the Plan or of events that require its review. The implementation of the European directive 2014/89 has not changed the legislative and administrative framework by imposing a form of planning and governance that replaces the pre-existing one but has added a higher level of planning, which arises as necessary to ensure a clear framework, coherent, and capable of pursuing the objectives of the various policies, also with a view to cross-border cooperation. At the level of the Campania Region, the administration is responsible for the adoption of a regional Plan for the use of the areas of the maritime state property (*demanio marittimo*) to regulate and enhance, for tourist-recreational purposes, the 450 kilometres of regional coast. The regional Plan fits into the broader scenario of the Integrated Maritime Policy of the European Union with the aim of pursuing integrated management and ensuring sustainable growth of coastal and marine ecosystems, subjected to strong settlement pressure, climate change, natural disasters and erosion.

There are a number of different administrative bodies that underpin marine governance acting at different levels (national, EU, local) in the Campania PS. Concerning the MSP the technical committee drawing the plan include representatives of Central and Regional administration (15 coastal regions) that are supported by researchers and technicians of national research centres and universities. For the achievement of the Marine Strategy goals, the MASE (Ministry of Environment and Energy Security) has implemented monitoring protocols and activities that are mainly managed by ISPRA (Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale). To support the sharing of knowledge and the monitoring of the sea of the Campania Region it has been recently promoted a regional network named "The Observatory of the Sea and Coastal Coast Foundation" which brings together 11 partners between public bodies, research institutions and universities. A visual reflection of the various national bodies that underpin marine governance in the Campania Planning Site can be viewed in the site's organogram (Figure 9).

The establishment of an MPA is preceded by the identification, through a specific regulatory provision, of a "marine candidate area". The marine candidate areas are identified pursuant to Laws no. 979/1982 and no. 394/1991. Once the technical process has been completed, the MPA is established with a Decree of the Minister of the Environment in agreement with the Minister of Economy and Finance which indicates the denomination and spatial delimitation of the area, the conservation and the protection discipline to which it is subjected. According to law no. 979/1982, MPAs are defined as marine environments which present a significant interest for their natural, geomorphological, physical, biogeochemical (with particular regard to marine and coastal flora and fauna) and for the scientific, ecological, cultural, educational and economic importance that they hold. Law 394/1991, "framework law on protected areas", partially modifying the provisions of the 1982 law. The main innovation was represented by the integration between the objective of environmental conservation and socio-economic development from a sustainable development perspective. In Italy, most MPAs include or have been implemented in proximity to a Natura 2000 site.

For the effective establishment of an MPA, it is necessary to have an updated framework of knowledge on the natural environment of interest, in addition to data relating to social and economic activities

taking place in the area. The Ministry of the Environment can benefit Universities, laboratories and research institutions for the acquisition of such knowledge and data. The studies are generally divided into two phases: in the first the existing literature on the area is examined; in the second phase, the necessary in-depth studies are carried out to collect the necessary data and information. As regards Natura 2000 sites, they are identified at a regional administrative level, on the basis of scientific studies. The MSP include specific objectives of environmental protection for the Campania Regional waters. They include biodiversity conservation and the application of management models fostering the touristic valorisation of MPAs without impairing environmental protection. However, in the implementation process of MSP, Italian MPAs have never been formally involved. This is also possibly because it is not yet fully understood that MSP is also a tool for environmental conservation. A relevant aspect that emerged also from interviews is the lack of national coordination to build an efficient network among national MPAs that can also promote conservation goals, including the achievement of the 30%-10% of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. The existent coordinated activities with local and/or national Institutions are mostly driven by the personal initiative of the Director.

Regarding MSP, there are several formal (institutional) and informal networks promoting dialogue and cooperation in the Mediterranean region, such as the UfM (Union for the Mediterranean) or the WestMED Initiative⁵. In line with the Barcelona and Berne conventions, Agenda 21, the Convention on Biological Diversity, the SPA/BD Protocol, and the Syracuse Charter on biodiversity, there is the important issue of improving knowledge of the deep environments (below the 200m isobath) of the area in order to direct adequate actions for the conservation of habitats and species present also beyond the national waters. Concerning fisheries a better conservation status of the marine environment can be achieved through the implementation of MAPs (multiannual management plans) for the GSA 8, 9, 10, 11 and the connected management objectives to minimize the environmental impacts of fishing activities. MedPAN⁶ is a Network of MPA managers in the Mediterranean which promotes guidelines, recommendations, good practices, practical tools, etc. also to support the development of management plans. There is a network at the Mediterranean level for the SPAMI (Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance) which represents MPAs declared in the frame of the Barcelona Convention. The network is organized by the RAC-SPA and financed by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, in which SPAMIs exchange good practices and meet to see how to resolve common issues.

One of the major challenges facing the marine governance planning process in the Campania region is the need to foster ecological connectivity among MPAs through the identification and protection of ecological corridors. A lack of consultation activity at the national level has been identified as another important weakness of the MPA national system.

Celtic Sea

Ireland's Maritime Spatial Plan was developed in 2021 and is supported by the MAP Act of 2021. The primary challenge in marine governance in Ireland is the pending formalization of MPA legislation. Presently, a key driving force for the development of MPAs is the necessity to safeguard marine environmental resources before the installation of ORE infrastructure. Following this, there will be a crucial need to harmonize the MPA Bill with the NMPF 2021 and the MAP Act 2021 to ensure their

⁵ (<https://westmed-initiative.ec.europa.eu/>)

⁶ <https://medpan.org/en>

effective implementation. However, this can be challenging, as government departments often operate in silos, making it difficult to integrate measures and policies across different departments.

The WFD, MSFD, and the Birds and Habitats Directives are other vital marine governance policies that are interconnected. As policy states, *“any reporting for the Water Framework Directive can be directly utilized for the MSFD, and any marine reporting for the Habitats Directive should feed into (descriptor) six and partially into (descriptor) one”*. Regarding the MSFD, one management official highlighted that *“it primarily focuses on reporting, but its actionable steps are limited, which is a critical aspect. At the European level, we need to concentrate more on utilizing science, data, and reporting to drive substantial changes”*. Additional pertinent policies encompass the Nature Restoration Directive, such as the Renewable Energy Directive and the Climate Act 2021.

In Ireland, marine protected sites have been designated under the Birds and Habitats Directives. The insufficient resources and lack of participation in the designation of protected sites have posed significant challenges in implementing and monitoring these areas. The MPA Bill aims to address this challenge, emphasizing the importance of participation and social justice in decision-making, particularly in relation to the Habitats Directive. It is anticipated that the MPA Bill, together with the MAP Act, will facilitate the co-location of marine activities and protection measures. Designated Maritime Area Plans (DMAPs), stemming from the MAP Act 2021, are expected to support this co-location by acting as management plans for maritime areas, considering the development of multi-activity areas and accounting for potential MPAs.

Transboundary concerns have been taken into account in the collaboration between Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the UK during the development of the NMPF 2021. Various departments collaborate with one another and engage external stakeholders, including scientists, the fishing industry, the ORE industry, and local communities. Formal working groups have further aided both national and transboundary partnerships. Public consultation played a crucial role in establishing the NMPF 2021 and is planned for use in the development of MPAs to discern the public's preferences for protected features. Nonetheless, a common challenge faced is the constraint of time and resources for engaging with diverse stakeholders and forums.

Lastly, monitoring MPAs and establishing trust and stewardship with the public may present challenges. However, it is hoped that the MPA Bill *“will incorporate stakeholder involvement throughout the process of identifying, designating, and managing MPAs, enabling the regulations and management framework for nationally designated MPAs to be developed in consultation and with the direct involvement of stakeholders, ensuring their active participation in the enforcement and compliance processes”*.

Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas

The Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site currently faces significant challenges in addressing policy gaps concerning MPAs, as both EU-mandated requirements and national policy issues remain unfulfilled. Efforts are underway to update policies in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, as the current Natura Network's marine areas cover approximately 18% of the country after their last revision in 2017. As a protected area, a government actor explained how, *“The Ministry of the Environment is currently implementing Special Environmental Studies to outline land use, terms, and activities within protected areas. Another ongoing program monitors species and habitats listed in the Habitats Directive Annexes. The Monitoring Program, set to conclude in 2026, will reassess the Natura*

2000 network [in the country] and guide its expansion. A project to map Marine Habitat Types in Natura 2000 areas lacking this information is also scheduled to start soon”.

A policy reformation is also emergent concerning MSP in Greece, as the country faces delays beyond the 2021 deadline when coastal EU countries were expected to establish Maritime Spatial Plans. Spatial planning (SP) government officials acknowledged that: *“The Strategy has already been formulated but not institutionalized”* and *“one [out of the four] Framework has not undergone public consultation yet [i.e. a necessary process for its institutionalization] and for the other three, studies have not even started”*. However, they appeared reassuring, as they mentioned that: *“Due to the infringement of the deadline by the EU, we will hurry and move quickly to finalize these frameworks”*. In the absence of finalized MSP frameworks, Regional Spatial Plans are employed to offer guidelines for spatial planning in the marine realm.

Transboundary cooperation is regarded as a valuable asset in policy development, with SP government officials highlighting that transboundary programs *“greatly assist in initiating such processes [i.e. related to formulation of policy]”*. The legislation also promotes transboundary collaborations by, as one policy actor explained, *“seeking the opinions of non-EU members in any possible way, not only through the Strategic Environmental Assessment [which is the step where neighbouring EU countries are asked to provide opinions on MSP] but also through forums like SPA/RAC, involving all Mediterranean countries”*. MPAs and MSP are integrated based on legislative procedures. A protected areas (PA) government official informed explained how *“for MSP within Natura 2000 areas, thorough impact assessments for the environmental impact of each use will be conducted. If negative, usage will be restricted, while impact-free activities will be allowed”*. MPAs are considered vital for MSP, taking into account the 30% target by 2030. However, full integration of MPAs into MSP implementation remains a work in progress as the national strategy remains a document of principles and general guidelines.

Southern North Sea

Of the four countries included in the SNS case study, two are federal states: Belgium and Germany. In both countries, MSP is a federal competency with some peculiarities. In Germany, the federal MSP concerns only the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ – up to 200 nautical miles), while the Territorial Sea (up to 12 nautical miles) are regulated by the coastal states. As a consequence, the tourism sector had little interest in the federal MSP and is more involved in the coastal states' planning of the territorial waters. In Belgium, fisheries mostly depend on the Flemish region, the federal state is in charge of safety regulations on ships for example, but all other regulations about fishing are a Flemish competency. Fisheries being an activity regulated at the European level, by the Common Fisheries Policy, the Flemish state is the one that transcribes the European regulations into Belgian (Flemish) laws.

The Netherlands and the UK are unitary states. In the Netherlands, one MSP covers the entire Dutch part of the North Sea and regulates all activities within it. In the UK, eleven marine areas were defined, each with its own marine plan. The areas that are within the scope of this analysis are the East Inshore and East Offshore Marine Plan Areas, for more information visit the website of the English Marine Management Organization about marine plan areas in England⁷. The following paragraphs provide detailed information about the MSP process in the SNS case study. This information was gathered

⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/marine-plan-areas-in-england>

from the official written sources (MSP documents and official websites), and interviews with policy-makers.

While all countries included in the SNS case study have an implemented MSP, some being at their second or third round, the process differs from one country to another. In Belgium, the current MSP is a 6-year plan, from 2020 until 2026, and is the country's second MSP, the first plan was implemented in 2014 until 2020. The MSP process is the charge of a ministry, the North Sea Cabinet, and of an administrative service, the Marine Environment Service. Until now, plans were to be renewed every six years, but starting with the next one (2026-2034), this period will be extended to eight years. The purpose of MSP in Belgium is to support the natural environment of the North Sea so that ecosystem services continue to be provided and support social and economic development (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2019b). A strong emphasis is put on the development of marine multi-use, referring to the combination of activities at sea. This is easily explained by the small size, yet intensive use, of the Belgian part of the North Sea. Belgian MPAs are fully integrated into the MSP, and one law currently accounts for both MPAs and other area designations (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2019a). The public research institute (RBINS – Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences) is strongly involved in the MSP process to provide scientific advice to policy makers. Additionally, all marine sectors are involved in the making of the plan, first by being represented by a governmental committee, then with exchanges with private entities, such as NGOs (4Seas being the umbrella for Belgian NGOs working on the Belgian part of the North Sea, also called the BPNS) and industries (Blue Cluster being the umbrella for industries working in the BPNS).

In Germany, the current MSP was implemented in 2021 and is the country's second MSP. The vision of the German MSP is to support coherent international planning and cooperation, take land-sea interactions into consideration, have a sustainable maritime economy, and ensure coordination of the various activities at sea (navigation, economic uses, research, etc.), all the while contributing to the protection and enhancement of the marine environment (The Federal Law Gazette, 2021). Amongst the mentioned economic uses, renewable energy production is singled-out, hence appears as a priority in the blue economy development vision. German MSP and MPA implementations are two independent processes, undertaken by two different federal agencies: the BSH for MSP and the BfN for MPAs. The integration of MPAs into the MSP is made by recognition of the MPAs areas in the plan, but their status is quite weak. While it is not currently the case, legally speaking maritime spatial planners could allocate another use on top of a MPA area. The current German MSP is the second plan (starting from 2021) and is to be updated every 10 years. However, it can be updated during this period to adjust some areas allocation, such as the allocation of OWFs areas. As in Belgium, scientific advice is provided, by the Thuenen research institute, and industrial sectoral interests are first represented by governmental organizations, then by private entities, and NGOs are also involved in the MSP process.

The Netherlands is currently in its third MSP, covering the period 2022-2027. The two previous ones (2009-2015 and 2016-2021) were similar in application for 5 years. The official document presenting the 2022-2027 MSP is a Policy Document called the "North Sea Programme 2022-2027". Its legal value consists of the statutory obligations under the Water Act, a national law that implements the European MSPD and the MSFD (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). The North Sea Programme 2022-2027 provides the framework for planning spatial use at sea, the MSP and the assessment framework for issuing permits. The Minister for Infrastructure and Water Management coordinates the Dutch North Sea policy and management, while the Rijkswaterstaat is the coordinating manager of the Dutch part of the North Sea. The current Dutch MSP has a strong focus on offshore wind farm development, as one of the main strategies in the Netherlands to attain climate objectives for 2050 is

through sustainable energy production (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). Because wind farms require a lot of space, in combination with other activities, ocean multi-use, is also strongly encouraged by the 2022-2027 MSP. For the protection and conservation of the marine ecosystem, nine MPAs are defined by the Dutch MSP. Actions to be taken regarding these MPAs (area expansion, drawing up of management plan, added regulations on activities, etc.) are listed in the North Sea Programme 2022-2027 (Government of the Netherlands, 2022).

In England, the East Inshore and East Offshore marine areas are regulated by one document and managed by the Marine Management Organisation (MMO). The two areas are next to each other, with the East Inshore referring to the Territorial Sea (up to 12 nautical miles) and the East Offshore referring to its juxtaposed EEZ (up to 200 nautical miles). The plans for the areas, made in 2014, were the first MSP in the UK. They have not been replaced since but have been updated on several occasions. The last update was in June 2021, according to the MMO website⁸ (GOV.UK, consulted on 21/08/23). The plans are meant to inform and guide regulation, management, use and protection of the marine areas, and are to be applied through decisions made by public authorities (HM Government, 2014). Their legal foundation lies in the Marine and Coastal Access Act, an English law requiring that public authorities make decisions in accordance with the marine policy in force, hence the “East Inshore and East Offshore Marine Plans” (HM Government, 2014) regarding marine activities in East Inshore and Offshore areas. The vision for England’s East marine plan is to achieve a sustainable, effective and efficient use of the marine area, supporting social and economic development of the region, by 2034. A strong emphasis is put on offshore wind energy production (HM Government, 2014). MPAs are reported in the East Inshore and East Offshore marine plans. Two types of MPAs are reported: NATURA 2000 (Birds or Habitats Directive) areas and Marine Conservation Zones (MCZs). MPAs are implemented and managed by different bodies than the MMO: Natural England and Joint Nature Conservation Committee. Although they all belong to the same department, DEFRA, the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs. The application and issuing of permits to and by the MMO must take MPA regulations into consideration (HM Government, 2014).

West Mediterranean

There are two main objectives of the Western Mediterranean Sea Planning Site: 1) examine transboundary scenarios on MSP and explore how coherent and robust conservation planning can meet 2030 targets at the regional level; and 2) assess the cumulative human pressures on EBSA areas and the risk for ecosystem services at the regional level. The following paragraphs are informed by key actors engaged in a co-development process with a high influence and high interest in the MSP processes, MPA designation processes and the outputs of the MarinePlan project in the Western Mediterranean Planning Site. The results show that the European Commission, National European Ministries and GFCM are the key-player stakeholders who have the highest influence and interest related to the regional outputs. Non-European Ministries can have high influence, yet they do not have MSP specific legislation to enforce, hindering their interest in this audit.

In the Western Mediterranean Sea, there are several simultaneous sectorial processes taking place with relevant implications in terms of MSP, but there is not currently any global MSP that covers all blue economy activities and conservation (Coll et al., 2013; Katsanevakis et al., 2015). Regarding EBSA, there are two transnational EBSAs already defined, but the consulted stakeholders consider that they are not currently directly used for management purposes. For example, one interview expert working

⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/marine-planning-in-england>

in transnational planning processes in the Mediterranean Sea said: *“We don’t really apply them ... they are designed by environmental ministers but our interlocutors are fisheries ministers, we don’t integrate them in our processes, so we see them as something positive of course, but we don’t have much to say about them”*.

From the national perspective, others pointed out that there are other very similar figures, yet not equal, in the context of some of the national MSPs. They also define interest areas from the ecological perspective but are not linked to concrete management measures. The coherence between the national and the EBSA approach more than in formal processes it is based on a personal basis *“the coherence between the national perspective and the international processes is facilitated by the fact that the team of people in the minister working in the definition of relevant national areas for biodiversity conservation at the national level and the team working with EBSA is the same”*. There are also two transnational FRAs implemented in the Western Mediterranean with concrete management plans in place, the *“Gulf of Lions FRA”*, where both France and Spain interests are affected, and the *“below 1000m depth FRA”*, relating to all countries in the region. The aim is to protect both EFHs and VMEs. They have been established by the GFCM. They are currently both under review with the aim of increasing the level of protection. There is also a new FRA being evaluated located at the Morocco-Algerian-Spanish frontiers (Cabliers Coral Mound FRA).

Another MSP policy process is linked to the Barcelona Convention. In the context of this Convention, the countries established a List of Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance (SPAMI's List). Most of them are small and nationally based, but two of them are of regional interest, the *“Pelagos Sanctuary for the Conservation of marine mammals”* (with French, Monaco and Italian interests) and the *“Cetaceans Migration Corridor in the Mediterranean”* (at Spanish EEZ International waters but with regional relevance), whose management plan is being developed. In the same areas, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) is in the process of approval of the *“North Western Mediterranean Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas”* management plan, which will introduce specific shipping restriction measures on both regional SPAMIs, in a coordinated action of Spain, France, Italy and Monaco, to protect marine mammals.

Considering all MPAs in this Planning Site and management plans associated with them, it can be observed that they are designed and implemented starting from the national perspective interests, not from a basin analysis perspective, and that there are low levels of fully or highly protected areas since many protection figures do not have approved and implemented management plans with different measures, respectively (Claudet et al., 2020). In all the national MSP processes, the transnational perspective is introduced through formal consultations with national neighbours’ administrations, as part of the environmental strategic consultation process. But more interestingly according to the interviewers, there are also informal previous meetings between technicians from the involved countries that they evaluate as relevant and useful.

As far as transboundary cooperation is concerned, it is important to mention the WestMED Initiative, where different countries (Algeria, France, Italy, Libya, Malta, Mauritania, Morocco, Portugal, Spain and Tunisia) collaborate in the context of the development of the blue economy. It is an initiative that is supported by the European Union with the support of the Union for the Mediterranean. The Western Mediterranean initiative has been defined by the interviewees as a *“scientific diplomacy”* structure useful *“where politics can not arrive”*, the political structure that supports its activity is a mix between *“foreign affairs representatives”* and *“the ministers in charge of blue economy”*, that in the Western Mediterranean presents a big diversity. In some countries, they are the same that are in charge of *fisheries*, in others blue economy depends on *transport*, and in some cases, there are specific

marine ministers. In several contexts, marine processes are unlinked with regional environmental processes.

Generally speaking, there is a perception of the increasing relevance of MSP processes *“The more relevant update on the (WestMed) new political agreement will be on promoting MSP, and this comes from a bottom-up approach, it is asked by the national governments also from the Southern Basin Countries i.e. from Morocco and Algeria...we will start from a very pragmatic approach: gathering data and identification of common challenges. We do not expect joint transnational planning at this point”*. In this endeavour, during 2023 it was created the MSP Community of Practice in the Med (MED-MSP-CoP) with the main objective of establishing permanent communication and dialogue across borders between experts on MSP (i.e. planners, technical experts, and researchers), and exchanging knowledge and relevant experiences in the region, to reach a shared perspective on topics of common interest on MSP and enhance the cooperation between the north and the south of the Mediterranean. The main two topics of common interest for the CoP are MSP as a key enabler for the implementation of national Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE) strategies and initiatives, and MSP supporting the extension, improved management and improved connection of MPAs and Other Effective Area-based Conservation Measures in the Mediterranean Sea. Finally, in terms of international MSP-related initiatives, the European Union is the leading funder in the WestMED Initiative (that includes a cooperation assistance mechanism) and it is also the main financial contributor to the GFCM.

Western Baltic Sea

In Denmark, the Marine Plan has been negotiated by the government with a broad majority. The agreement has the character of a voting agreement, and with the conclusion of the agreement, the Minister for Industry, Business and Financial Affairs will then issue Denmark's maritime spatial plan, which is specifically implemented by executive order based on the Maritime Spatial Planning Act (the Marine Planning Act). The parties to the agreement note that the implementation of regulation of fishing in protected and strictly protected areas where other EU member states have fishing rights will have to take place following negotiations with the member states concerned in accordance with the rules of the EU's common fisheries policy. After the conclusion of the agreement, the maritime spatial plan must be subject to an environmental assessment, after which it must be subject to public consultation. In this context, a neighbourly consultation (Espoo consultation) will also be carried out. Subsequently, the Executive Order on Marine Planning will be issued, and marine plan supplements with the agreed amendments will be submitted for public consultation. This will happen no later than September 30, 2023. The updated maritime spatial plan has legal effect from the date of consultation of the maritime spatial plan. The parties to the agreement will be presented with the outcome of the public consultation before the maritime spatial plan is finally issued. The maritime spatial plan is then valid for 10 years. No later than 4 years into the planning period, the parties to the agreement will be invited to a discussion of the maritime spatial plan, including on the basis of an increased data base, the upcoming raw materials plan, the recommendations of the Fisheries Commission, the EU Commission's initiatives in this area, the ongoing offshore wind screening, developments in CO2 storage and experiences with coexistence.

In Germany, the federal MSP concerns only the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ – up to 200 nautical miles), while the Territorial Sea Zone (up to 12 nautical miles) is regulated by the coastal states. As a consequence, the tourism sector had little interest in the federal MSP and is more involved in the coastal states' planning of the territorial waters. The current MSP was implemented in 2021 and is the country's second MSP. The vision of the German MSP is to support coherent international planning

and cooperation, take land-sea interactions into consideration, have a sustainable maritime economy, and ensure coordination of the various activities at sea (navigation, economic uses, research, etc.), all the while contributing to the protection and enhancement of the marine environment (The Federal Law Gazette, 2021). Amongst the mentioned economic uses, renewable energy production is singled-out, hence appears as a priority in the blue economy development vision. German MSP and MPA implementations are two independent processes, undertaken by two different federal agencies: the BSH for MSP and the BfN for MPAs. The integration of MPAs into the MSP is made by recognition of the MPAs areas in the plan, but their status is quite weak. While it is not currently the case, legally speaking maritime spatial planners could allocate another use on top of a MPA area. The current German MSP is the second plan (starting from 2021) and is to be updated every 10 years. However, it can be updated during this period to adjust some areas allocation, such as the allocation of Offshore Windfarm (OWF) areas. Scientific advice is provided by research institutes (e.g., Thuenen), and industrial sectoral interests are first represented by governmental organizations, then by private entities. NGOs are also involved in the MSP process.

3.3 PARTICIPATION AND STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE

This sub-section demonstrates how stakeholder participation is operationalised in each of the Planning Site areas. Information is provided on how external stakeholders are involved in participation processes, who the most influential stakeholders are, and how such actors exert their influence. This involves assessments of the formal consultation processes that operate, what engagement methods beyond consultation are utilised, and the degrees to which policies have changed as a result of participation processes.

Azores

The Blue Azores process was initiated in 2019, with six core phases. The first was termed as the ‘visioning phase’, which defined a common vision for the MPA Offshore network, including principles, goals, and objectives. The process continued with the second phase, which involved a data analysis phase to evaluate existing spatial data regarding natural values, and ocean uses. Following this, phase three initiated what was determined as the ‘negotiation phase’. Once this had been completed, two further phases – the evaluation phase and an agreement phase to endorse a specific scenario – were operationalised. Finally, phase six of the process involved the proposal of the offshore MPA network for public consultation. This involved a range of stakeholder engagement events and consultation activities. One interviewee, who works on MSP in the Azores, explained how they have *“tried to develop genuine and active engagement from the start. So, in 2018 and 2019, in the pre planning stage, we had three stakeholder engagement workshops. This helped to create the stakeholder network with more than 800 contacts”*. These workshops were replicated across the Azores islands, ensuring high levels of participation by local stakeholders, businesses and communities. One challenge to the stakeholder process relates to the fact that the Azores is an archipelago. One interviewee explained how *“we have a difficulty in relation to the geographical dispersion of our islands, it forces us to host multiple events and to accept that it will be a time-consuming process”*. The opening workshops on each island focused on defining a vision and the objectives of the MSP.

A second workshop focused on tackling the needs and problems of specific sectors, whilst also providing space for actors to clarify their thoughts on the future. The future evolution of marine activities in the Azores and, in particular, the potential conflicts between such activities and the environment, was a key point of discussion amongst stakeholders. The final workshop was focused on the mapping of potential protected areas. As one member of the planning team explained, *“we have achieved a lot with stakeholders, especially through working groups where we may not have engaged the whole population, but at least interested parties have been involved”*. The same interviewee clarified how *“the working groups tackle specific sectoral issues and are informed by their considerations”*. In addition to the workshops, it was stated that interviews were also conducted with key figures. A marine planner explained how interviews involved the use of tools, such as ‘seasketch’, *“in an attempt to minimize the knowledge gap regarding the use of the space by some activities. This mainly involved those from maritime tourism and fisheries too, because we lack ecosystem data and do not have the same levels of environmental data across all of the islands”*. Through the identification of knowledge gaps such as this, the regional planning system can focus on target areas that require attention.

A final point that emerged from discussions with current marine management actors in the Azores related to the topic of ‘stakeholder fatigue’. As one official explained, *“I believe that this [stakeholder*

fatigue] is a real danger with attempting to consistently involve a broad range of actors and sectoral representatives in all consultation events". It was also mentioned by a government actor, who asserted that "we are trying to involve people in several initiatives and that is where I believe we are starting to see some stakeholder fatigue ... We must work out different techniques of managing this". As more active forms of engagement are developed and operationalised, it appears clear that the issue of fatigue may become a significant challenge. This is a particularly pressing issue for regions such as the Azores, which has a relatively small network of ocean users. It was noted by officials that they are aware of the pressing need to find solutions to overcome potential stakeholder fatigue, with great alignment between different projects and initiatives one proposed idea.

Bay of Biscay

In Spain, Directive 2014/89/UE and Royal Decree 363/2017 give special importance to the involvement of the key agents and economic sectors in the development of national MSP. In this sense, it was planned to celebrate workshops or participatory events in the five demarcations with representatives of the sectors throughout 2020. This participation plan was cancelled by the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. For this reason, the meeting was celebrated online, in December 2020, with more than 270 people. During this online meeting, a presentation of the status of the plan was made, answering the questions asked by the representatives of the different sectors. In January 2020, the environmental body (General Directorate for Environmental Quality and Evaluation) began consultations with the affected public administrations and interested persons, on the draft plan together with the initial strategic document. In total, 73 contributions were received, and in November 2020, the Scope Document prepared by the environmental body was received. In June 2021, the draft Royal Decree approved the MSP plans of the five Spanish marine demarcations which were opened to the Audience and public information. Finally, 115 allegations were received: 42 from administrations, 19 from industry, 42 from associations and 12 from individuals. From July 2021 to September 2021, the same text, together with the strategic environmental study, was submitted to the consultation process with the affected public administrations and interested parties (according to Law 21/2013 for Environmental Evaluation), receiving 118 allegations: 42 from administrations, 4 from industry, 20 from associations and foundations and 2 from individuals. In addition, the affected Ministries were consulted on the draft royal decree approving the MSP plans of the five Spanish marine demarcations, during its processing.

The consultation of the Environmental Advisory Council was carried out at the meeting in October 2021. No additional observations were received from those received through the allegations resulting from the public consultation processes. The consultation of the Inter-ministerial Commission for Marine Strategies was carried out at the meeting in March 2022. No additional observations were received from those received through the allegations resulting from the public consultation processes. Apart from the mandatory consultation, the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge of Spain, from the Sub-directorate for the Protection of the Sea, celebrated thematic ad-hoc groups/meetings with non-sectorial stakeholders, with local government administrations, by subject, initiatives at the demand of sectors (i.e., new sectors such as marine renewable energies and with fishermen) due to high demand, at a technical level and at a high political level. They also participated in several conferences; according to one of the most important challenges is to meet expectations and meet deadlines with the European Commission, reconcile conflict resolution and meet deadlines. They are going to design a better participation strategy, cohering the participation activities, better structuring, avoiding conflict and improving the feedback. After public consultation and after considering all the allegations, all the involved sectors agreed with the final

version of the national MSP, except the fishing sector. The marine renewable energy industry has been the most injured party by the reduction of 30% of the polygons identified for this activity. The fishing sector has been the most reactive sector.

In France, the Coordinator Prefets support the secretariat of the Conseils Maritimes de Façade, a consultative organism bringing together around 80 stakeholders representing: national authorities and agencies; local and regional authorities (regions, cities, etc.); blue economy companies and organisations; trade unions; non-governmental organisations. The Coordinator Prefets are supported by Inter-regional Directorates for the Sea (Directions Interrégionales de la Mer – DIRM) in each sea basin, covering the entire coastline of metropolitan France. The maritime council is not a consultative body, but it is permanent and looks after the whole process; this is, the process and the implementation of the process. In addition to the process described above, there is a formal consultation of stakeholders and the general public. This takes place ahead of the planning and when the planning is ready, thus a two-stage process. For the first step, the National Council for Public Debates is consulted by CEREMA if they want to organize the public debate. For the second stage, the National Committee takes care of the consultation process. This is a very costly process involving consultations and workshops. As described above, the organizational structures are in place for the participation of stakeholders in the debates. Nonetheless, the involvement of these and their influence on decision-making differs from group to group. Some of these groups are influential because they are well organized at the national level, such as, for example, the wind farm sector; in other cases, the groups are organized too and have wide access to the media and decision-makers due to their capacity to mobilize people against plans affecting their interests, e.g. fishing sector. In turn, other groups such as environmental groups have less capacity to react, likely because some topics that are in their agendas are not on the debate in the region, e.g. bycatch of mammals. Tourism in turn is not represented in the debates. Thus, it seems that despite the institutional set-up providing the possibilities for all groups to participate in the debates and consultations only those that have the interest and capacity to organise themselves are able to be active in the debate and influence decisions. This appears to be independent of the economic size of the sector. For example, tourism versus fishing.

Campania

In the Campania region, MSP formal consultations are put in place through the MSP technical committee. This has developed internal consultations. The Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport published the documents relating to the Maritime Space Management Plans public consultation from 15 September to 30 October 2022. However, it is not clear how the results of this consultation have been considered and eventually integrated into the MSP. Concerning the establishment of new MPAs, the Ministry of Environment through ISPRA has put in place a formal process of consultation and involvement of key stakeholders (e.g., professional artisanal fishers, leisure fishers, sailing and boating, and diving centres). Once established, it is not an obligation of MPAs to carry out formal stakeholder consultations as there is no mandatory requirement in this regard. It is the responsibility of MPA directors to promote stakeholder engagement through formal and informal processes. However, the interviewed Directors documented continuous interactions with stakeholders with outcomes that are incorporated into the management plan of the MPA.

The most used engagement methods are the organization of workshops, community engagement events, and knowledge share/communication or consultation sessions. MPAs create links and collaborations with research institutions/environmental agencies to develop monitoring. Research

activities are allowed after specific requests and assessment of their relevance. National sectoral working groups have been organized in the last years for the development of specific guidelines (e.g., anchoring or mooring, boating and sailing, diving). The management of a MPA is a highly adaptive process and important regulations have been introduced after stakeholder consultations. A key aspect of the stakeholder consultation process is that it strongly promotes a change in their mentality and level of environmental awareness. This is an essential requirement to adopt a co-management system that makes the stakeholders protagonists of the MPA and ensures that the management regulations are respected.

MPAs establish scientific collaborations with different research institutions to support MPAs for the achievement of the conservation goals of EU Directives (e.g. Habitat Directive, MSFD) and integrate them into the MPA management plans. The MSP key actors are those participating in the MSP national technical committee (i.e., the Ministries dealing with marine-maritime issues, and 15 Italian maritime regions). No specific stakeholder group is excluded from consultation during MPA establishment and management. In the implementation of new MPAs, in Italy there is a formal process of consultation and involvement of stakeholders of the main users of the seas (professional artisanal fishers, leisure fishers, sailing and boating, and diving centres). However, at a local level, issues can arise with specific groups of stakeholders.

Celtic Sea

The development of Ireland's National Marine Planning Framework in 2021 involved extensive public participation and stakeholder engagement (Government of Ireland, 2023). The National Marine Planning Framework was established to unify all marine-based activities for the first time, outlining the government's vision, objectives, and policies for each marine activity. To ensure efficiency, sustainability, and alignment with the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive 2014/89/EU, a transparent process involving stakeholders in maritime planning was implemented. A Stakeholder Advisory Group, chaired by the minister of state, was formed to facilitate participation in the MSP process by relevant stakeholders from economic, environmental, and social sectors. Its purpose was to leverage the potential of various sectors, including representation from public, business, environmental, social, and knowledge-based domains, in guiding strategic decisions for marine spatial plans. This group encompassed representatives from environmental NGOs, professional bodies, and technical planning experts.

Members of the Stakeholder Advisory Group were nominated by stakeholder organizations at the invitation of the Minister of state. Each participant represented their organization or sector, ensuring that all relevant stakeholders were consulted and encouraged to contribute to the planning process. Additionally, informal engagements, like interactions on social media, a Green Schools poster competition supported by the DHLGH (which received over 1000 submissions), and informal discussions during coffee breaks in formal meetings were conducted. The MSP team also invited the public and stakeholders via Twitter to submit marine photographs for potential inclusion in the draft plan. Marine spatial planning strives for transparent stakeholder involvement in maritime activities. The aim is to create strategic, concise plans informed by effective public and stakeholder participation to ensure widespread support for implementation. As one marine planner emphasized during interviews, *"we recognized from the beginning that we could not write a plan without people's input because it's impossible for our team to know everything about everything in the maritime area. That's just not how planning works. It has to be collaborative and it has to take advantage of the information that's out there. And that's partly science. But in the real world, you need to listen to people and*

understand how people are using space and you can't do that if you don't let people tell you". The draft National Marine Planning Framework underwent significant revisions following extensive public consultation. The comprehensive public engagement process played a pivotal role in shaping the final NMPF.

Regarding influence, though specific names are not provided, it is evident that stakeholders from diverse sectors exerted substantial input. This included fisheries, aquaculture, energy, tourism, sports, local authorities, as well as environmental NGOs like Bird Watch Ireland, SWAN, Coastwatch, An Taisce, and the Irish Whale and Dolphin Group among others. Their impact was felt through active participation in the Advisory Group and their contributions to the consultation process. The findings of the interviews note that no stakeholder was excluded from the consultation process. Similarly, direct engagement with a wide range of stakeholders (e.g., port authorities, local authorities, sports and recreation organizations, renewable energy sector, environmental groups etc.) in the marine sector was evident with a visible and active presence on social media platforms.

Between March and July 2018, the MSP Advisory Team organized public engagement events in nearly all coastal counties across Ireland, drawing almost 350 attendees. These events aimed to raise awareness about the MSP concept, the government's plan to develop the NMPF, details on public engagement, and a timeline for the various phases of the NMPF development process. Public consultation on the NMPF Baseline Report took place for three months from September 18th to December 14th, 2018. Five regional events were held to launch the Baseline Report and emphasize the importance of public participation in the MSP process. Over 170 submissions were received on the NMPF Baseline Report, significantly influencing the content of the NMPF. Public consultation on the draft NMPF commenced in November 2019, with an additional seven coastal regional events taking place between November 2019 and March 2020. Due to Covid-19 related restrictions, the final public consultation event was held online in April 2020. In addition to these public events, the Marine Planning Policy and Legislation team of the DHLGH continued to promote awareness, understanding, and public participation in the planning process throughout the consultation process, arranging or participating in over 150 conferences, seminars, and stakeholder events. The consultation approach taken by Ireland in developing the NMPF has been highlighted in significant European Union documents, strongly validating the comprehensive approach taken during its development.

Stakeholder participation and influence are equally pivotal in the development and management of the MPA bill. An advisory group was convened to provide independent expert advice and recommendations on the processes required and the challenges to be addressed in expanding Ireland's MPA network. This group facilitated the sharing of knowledge and perspectives on MPAs from more than 100 key societal, community, business, and sectoral stakeholders. The process involved two consultative approaches: an online questionnaire and online focus groups. Once the MPA bill and the Ocean Environment Policy Statement are published, plans are underway to subject them to a rigorous public consultation process. These consultation processes will refine the roadmap to MPA designation and implementation process in terms of what and where to protect in the Celtic Sea and Ireland's maritime area.

Overall, stakeholder engagement was executed through an inclusive and transparent process involving a wide range of sectors. This ensured that views and feedback from all relevant stakeholders were incorporated into the development of the NMPF and the MPA bill. Stakeholders play a substantial role in shaping MSP and MPA policies, and their implementation in both Ireland and the Celtic Sea. Their active engagement fosters a sense of ownership and stewardship, which is crucial for achieving long-term planning and conservation goals.

Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas

The primary method of stakeholder participation in the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site is through the public consultation process, which is mandatory for various aspects such as law drafts, Special Environmental Studies, and development projects within protected areas. Both agencies and individuals can provide comments on published documents. A PA government official emphasized that *“All concerns raised during consultation are addressed [in the final decision], including opinions on environmental impacts”*. However, some scientific advisors of the ministry express discomfort about the low level of engagement with scientific institutions, feeling that their suggestions are not adequately considered. They report that: *“Although they expected some input from us, for implementing strategies, they later ignored that. The interaction seemed to revolve more around questioning rather than fostering a constructive dialogue and making progress”* or *“Management appears to disregard scientific data, as our suggestions are either not accepted or disregarded altogether”*.

At the local level, stakeholder involvement mainly centres on local advisory committees that lack an institutional role or informal partnerships between Management Units, local authorities, and the public. These interactions have shown favourable outcomes, particularly in regions where Management Units or Environmental organizations have established a long-term presence and operation. As an example of that, an MPA manager shared their experience, stating: *“[Twenty years ago] there was a significant portion, about 85%, who displayed no willingness to cooperate and even resorted to chasing us with guns. Thanks to the diligent efforts of the Management Body back then, this percentage gradually decreased, and now approximately 60% of people are on board with cooperation”*.

For MSP, stakeholder engagement is facilitated through the National Spatial Planning Council, where apart from representatives of agencies and professional branches that officially participate in the board, relevant stakeholders related to MSP can engage in the dialogue without the right to vote. In addition to formal processes, stakeholder engagement for MSP is also facilitated through EU projects, which hold meetings and workshops to exchange knowledge and integrate stakeholders' opinions into planning and policy processes. However, the government's scientific advisors express lingering distrust regarding the integration of stakeholders' opinions in decision-making processes. Stakeholder participation and approval of legislative and management actions are considered the highest priority for MPA management implementation. Local engagement is considered crucial for success, and regions with a long history of protection and management have reported positive stakeholder interactions. A PA governmental official, commenting on the reactions to the expansion of the MPA network in 2017, stated that: *“In areas where there were environmental organizations or management bodies that informed the public, they were more positive and receptive to it. In places where people were informed for the first time [when the decision has already been made], there were reactions”*. When it comes to stakeholder influence on decision-making, there was no consensus among interviewees; however, it was indicated by respondents that industrial sectors such as fisheries, aquaculture, and renewable energy may wield greater influence.

Southern North Sea

In Belgium, public consultation is a long-standing practice, it is well infused in the political culture of the country. As stated by an interviewed policy-maker, *“Belgium is a country of consultation”*. Before

public consultation, informal exchanges happen in the making of an MSP draft. Currently, the 2026-2034 planning has started, and it was launched by a kick-off event gathering all major stakeholders of the BPNS (including RBINS, 4Seas and the Blue Cluster). Then comes a written request for stakeholders to formulate their wishes and ideas. The propositions are reviewed and the most promising ones are selected for further discussion. Then round tables are organized with relevant sectors to discuss potential use conflicts (which are numerous because of the size and activity intensity of the BPNS) and reach acceptable compromises when possible. After this first informal process, a pre-draft is made and taken into public (formal and legally requested consultation). The government is required to hold a public event open to all public, and coastal communities are encouraged to hold their own event to present the draft and provide feedback. The outcome of this public consultation is reported upon in an open-access document. Both informal and formal consultations have led to changes in the drafts in the past processes. All stakeholders participate in the Belgian MSP implementation process, although some are better organized than others.

In Germany, public consultation is less common. In the making of the second German MSP (2021-2031), policymakers took the initiative to have an informal stakeholder consultation process. This was a rather innovative initiative for Germany and took the form of informal meetings and e-mail exchanges with relevant stakeholders. Based on this review, a first pre-draft was designed and taken into formal public consultation. Because of the impact of Covid-19, this took the form of an online event which had a high participation rate and provided valuable feedback. A second draft was made with the integration of the public consultation feedback, and was presented to the federal government. The federal government then made final changes in both textual and spatial designation. In the first German MSP, fisheries did not wish to be involved because they saw themselves as losers of the process, but they got more involved in the second plan although the sector is quite unhappy with the direction of modern policies. The offshore wind sector and the nature conservation sector have conflicting uses and requests when it comes to MSP in Germany, and it was one of the major discussions in the stakeholder consultation process. Because of the current energy crises, the offshore wind sector is often given priority over nature conservation and fisheries. The general public rarely gets involved in the MSP process, likely because it only concerns the EEZ which does not directly affect citizens.

In the Netherlands, broad participation was sought in the making of the last MSP (22-27). All information reported in the following paragraph is described in the “North Sea Programme 2022-2027” (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, stakeholder participation was done in a digital format. Online meetings were held with interested parties, to go over interim results of subject areas, and share their views on future offshore wind farms locations and general preferences over space allocation. Local authorities were consulted multiple times and actively contributed to land-sea interaction considerations. Additionally, an informal coordination process took place with neighbouring countries from late 2020-early 2021. Meetings and consensus-based consultations were held simultaneously with the North Sea Consultative Body (IDON), the body in charge of the interdepartmental coordination and implementation of North Sea policies in the Netherlands. Ultimately, the final draft was submitted to public consultation for 6 months (March until September 2021). Because this MSP has a strong focus on offshore wind energy production development, a Supplementary Draft for the designation of new wind farm zones was put together, and similarly submitted to consultation from the IDON, the general public and neighbouring countries. The neighbouring countries were given an English translation of the document and were given a month of official consultation period. After taking into consideration received feedback from all parties, a final version of the MSP was designed and adopted in March 2022 (Government of the Netherlands, 2022).

During the preparation process of the East England marine plans, several stakeholder engagement and consultation events were held by the MMO, following a stakeholder participation strategy. These events were in-person workshops, meetings and public drop-in sessions. Decision-maker workshops were held, and participants included public bodies representing sectoral interests (nature conservation, fisheries, etc.) (MMO, 2013). Additionally, sectoral stakeholders were consulted when the plan draft was conceived, their concerns were reported on and addressed, and their feedback was taken into account in the making of the final draft (MMO, 2012).

West Mediterranean

Some of the key players identified as high-influence stakeholders are National countries, International NGOs, International professional associations and economic clusters and European Union consultative bodies (MEDAC). In terms of national MSP and MPA participation, in European countries, there are simultaneous national MSP and MPA planning processes taking place. In all of them, there are formal procedures for stakeholder participation, but the consulted national experts consider that they are too rigid and not enough to properly address in a positive and constructive way the concerns of some of the stakeholders. In some occasions, stakeholder participation is too reactive and starts to be actively involved, once the decision is in the last stages so changes are more difficult to introduce. In non-European national MSPs and MPAs participation processes are more limited, stakeholder influence is structured and the participation of social stakeholders is lower, but new initiatives are starting to be developed and there is an increasing interest in MSP.

In the case of international multilateral planning processes (such as those taking place in the context of the GFCM or IMO), there are also formal processes of participation of stakeholders, but the interview experts point out that there are also informal networks and contacts that are very useful, and in these cases the role of the international institutional “secretariats” as facilitators is crucial. As a member of these structures said *“we try to promote dialogue in a continuous way and arrive to informal agreements between all the stakeholders so once we arrive to the political decision formal bodies things have already been previously discussed or at least there is a good level of knowledge”*. The GFCM provides an interesting case of techno-political bottom-up approach *“any stakeholder can suggest the creation of a Fisheries Restricted Area at the technical level. There is a formal clear procedure with a template to do it. Any proposal will be discussed at the technical level, and then if it is considered meaningful from the technical perspective it will go to the political level where it will be discussed and accepted, modified or rejected”*. *“Clearly stakeholders’ participation has influenced in current management measures”*.

European Commission plays a major role in all the basin as a “leading partner” in many of the initiatives. However, there is still a clear division North-South in terms of capacities and involvement in decision-making. A key challenge at the basin level is the integration of all the processes at a regional or transboundary scale since there is a low level of integration between international transnational institutions planning processes (GFCM, UNEP processes, IMO). Their engagement is conducted by their secretariats, who participate as observers in the other planning processes, and they are invited to explain the new planning decisions once they are done. Finally, a small number of international NGOs participate regularly -with different figures according to the process- in most of the transboundary planning processes taking place in the Western Mediterranean, and MEDAC participate in those specifically linked with fisheries.

Western Baltic Sea

In Denmark, the proposed Marine Plan was subjected to a public hearing. An extensive list of public and private stakeholders as well as private persons had the opportunity to comment on the proposed plan. The ca. 250 hearing comments are publicly available. In the making of the second German MSP (2021-2031), diverse stakeholders, the public and the neighbouring countries have been involved in a multistep consultation process. The process also included thematic workshops on shipping, marine conservation, fisheries, underwater cultural heritage, defence and raw materials. Based on the results of the multi-consultation steps and the Strategic Environmental Assessment, the federal government made final changes in both textual and spatial designation and allowed a last opportunity to comment on it. Like in Denmark, all comments ($n=576$) from the consultation process are publicly available. While fisheries stayed out of the process in the first German MSP due to mistrust and the feeling of not being heard, they engaged in the second MSP. Nevertheless, the sector is still quite dissatisfied with the direction of modern policy. The offshore wind energy sector and the conservation sector have conflicting interests and requests when it comes to MSP in Germany, which was one of the main points of discussion in the stakeholder consultation process. Due to the current energy crisis, the offshore wind sector is often given priority over nature conservation and fisheries. The public is rarely involved in the MSP process, probably because it only concerns the EEZ, which does not directly affect citizens.

3.4 REFLEXIVITY AND ADAPTIVE CAPACITY

This sub-section demonstrates how the effectiveness of current policy is being monitored and reviewed. In doing so, it illustrates how evaluation processes are conducted, what this suggests about the adaptive capacity of policy-makers, and if previous successes (or failures) have informed change in the Planning Site regions. The information presented includes insight into the degree to which formal monitoring or evaluation approaches are used to measure the impact of policies relating to MSP and MPAs, and how these are operationalised. There is also interesting information revealed regarding the major challenges that have been encountered in the past when developing new marine governance policies and how these have impacted policy development. Furthermore, reference is made to any solutions that have been utilised in the Planning Sites to respond to emergent challenges.

Azores

In the Azores, several innovative solutions have been operationalised to correct for previous failings and time-pressured objectives. For instance, identifying areas of ecological relevance, such as those that fit the FAO criteria for defining VME or the CBD criteria for identifying EBSAs, is currently of utmost importance. To implement efficient management measures that would ensure the protection of the natural heritage in commitment to sustainable use of marine resources and the implementation of the Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the UN Biodiversity 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development the Regional Government of the Azores signed a memorandum of understanding over the 'Blue Azores' Program, focused on promoting the conservation and sustainable use of resources, by declaring 30% of the EEZ of the Azores as MPAs of which 15% should be strictly protected. Due to the current political agenda, the Azores Government aims to finalize the identification of the relevant deep-sea areas by the end of 2023. With the development of the Azor drift-cam, a cost-effective video platform designed to conduct rapid appraisals of deep-sea benthic habitats down to 1,000 m depth, and partnerships with the international scientific community, the amount of information regarding the composition and spatial distribution of benthic communities in the Azores was significantly enlarged over the last four years. Consequently, the Azores Deep Sea Research Group partnered with the Government of the Azores to develop a systematic conservation planning approach to inform the discussions on the identification of priority areas for conservation. Preliminary results showed that although existing biodiversity data can be used to produce transparent, data-driven and science-based scenarios, substantial gaps in scientific knowledge still exist, hampering the proper development of systematic conservation planning approaches aimed at informing management and policy. In order to fill these knowledge gaps, there is a need to continue mapping benthic communities inhabiting seamounts, ridges and island slopes that have not been explored before, among many other needs.

Bay of Biscay

In Spain, Section V of the national MSP (POEMs) includes the application, evaluation, and monitoring of the plans consisting of the analysis of the evolution of the different uses and activities in the marine environment, the effectiveness and possible deficiencies of the approved national MSP, thereby facilitating adaptive management and guiding steps towards review and update of the MSP, in 6 years review cycle, coinciding with Spanish Marine Strategies cycle reviews. This is because national MSP are nourished by socioeconomic, and environmental status and information that is transmitted to the POEMs from the Spanish Marine Strategies. The POEMs guarantee that the uses in marine areas are

compatible with the environmental objectives of the Spanish Marine Strategies. The POEMs are a measure of the strategies and share the scope of application. So, the objectives of the sectors should be long-term objectives, regardless of the political situation, to guarantee involvement and investment (i.e., the Marine Renewable Energy industry).

In France, the Secretary of State for the Sea is the national authority responsible for the overall planning of maritime space. Specifically, the Ministry is charged with ensuring the coherence of strategic plans at the national level; consulting stakeholders' national representatives; and reporting strategic plans to the European Commission. CEREMA provides technical expertise to assess the environmental and socio-economic impacts of various projects and activities in the marine realm.

The centre conducts research and develops methodologies, tools, and guidelines to support MSP processes through planning, implementation and monitoring. CEREMA works closely with government agencies, regional authorities, research organizations, and stakeholders, to foster collaboration and coordination in MSP. CEREMA develops tools such as spatial planning software, decision-support systems, and guidelines for assessing environmental impacts, managing maritime activities, and integrating multiple uses of marine space.

Campania

The fundamental purposes of the MSP monitoring program are to allow the monitoring of the effectiveness of the Plan (achievement of the declared qualitative or quantitative objectives) and the monitoring of the progress of the Plan actions. Where the plan objectives are not expressed in the formula of a target to be achieved (declared in quantitative or qualitative terms) the usefulness of the monitoring program is also that of identifying appropriate indicators which can show the trend of the phenomena relating to the objective under examination to understand whether the evolution of the situation is positive or negative. In terms of environmental protection, the current national MSP foresaw the adoption of analytical tools for analysis and continuous monitoring of the potential cumulative impacts of human activities on the environmental components (in synergy with the provisions of the MSFD and the Natura 2000 Directives) as well as conflicts/synergies between human uses. It recommends also the drafting of a National Environmental Restoration Plan, identifying the priority areas to be restored and the restoration measures and methods to be adopted, in a synergistic and subsidiary relationship with the implementation and monitoring process of the MSP. MPAs monitor the conservation status of habitats and species. It is an activity that is not carried out in a systematic way because there is no ordinary funding and/or dedicated personnel with stable positions and specific skills dedicated to it, even if there are funds for the marine strategy and the habitat directive. However, the monitoring is largely linked to the attaining of external funds and the involvement of research institutions that support the AMP.

In the management of MPAs, some managerial and political administrative problems have arisen linked, in particular, to the lack of personnel with stable positions who support the director in the management of the AMP. The personnel working in all Italian MPAs are paid on projects. The Director is the only figure with a guaranteed salary. The Ministry does not authorize the use of funds for ordinary management of the AMP for personnel expenses. In theory, therefore, the director must deal with all the different needs, from administrative problems to technical-scientific ones. One recent critical element is coming from the request from the Ministry of the Environment to extend the management presently addressing nationally designated MPAs also outside of the Natura 2000 sites in spatial continuity with the MPA. This request apparently does not translate into additional funding and support. Besides Natura 2000 management, another relevant issue, is the substantial lack of

involvement of MPA Directors in all decisions and activities relative to the spatial context in which they are embedded. What is outside the MPA is under the control of other institutions, never contacting them. However, it has been also recalled the potential importance of MPAs as control sites to assess the state of health of our seas. Therefore, the role of MPAs is no longer only local-national but has an international relevance to assess the state of implementation of the EU directives (e.g. MSFD, Habitat Directive). The future challenge will be therefore to make the role of MPAs more efficient and structured in the context of global marine protection. Among the main future challenges in terms of conservation, there will certainly be climate change and invasive species, for which it is also necessary to put in place monitoring and control systems.

The effective development of an MSP in Italian waters depends on the political will to adopt it and develop a policy for Italian seas in the short term, addressing all implementation needs and deciding how to review the objectives. Italy is lagging behind on this issue and a European infringement procedure is underway.

Celtic Sea

In Ireland, the effectiveness of current MSP and MPA policies undergo formal monitoring and review. Both the NMPF 2021 and MPA legislation incorporate provisions for stakeholder participation, which are integral to their respective review processes. These evaluation procedures engage advisory groups established by the DHLGH. These groups offer independent expert advice and recommendations for expanding Ireland's MPA network and implementing the NMPF 2021. Such processes reflect a high degree of adaptive capacity among policy-makers, actively seeking input and insights from stakeholders.

Remarkably, economic development has become a catalyst for the introduction of MPAs. Initial concerns about the feasibility of ORE until the conservation aspect was addressed acted as an unconventional driving force for the MSP development process. The development of Ireland's NMPF has responded to evolving demands, particularly in addressing the demands to develop the ORE sector. Likewise, the Global Biodiversity Framework's 30 by 30 targets have influenced the impending publication of Ireland's MPA bill, which is expected to become law before the end of the first quarter of 2024. However, a challenge persists in harmonizing these sectoral policies to ensure that ORE development and MPA expansion are mutually beneficial for both people and nature. Challenges in policy development and implementation of adaptive approaches consist of difficulties in enforcement, varying degrees of political will, and divergent stakeholder objectives. Climate change, legislative or policy shifts, sectoral pressures, and community objections have all impacted policy development in Ireland in one way or another. Nevertheless, the ongoing stakeholder engagement and consultation processes indicate that policymakers are actively seeking solutions to these challenges. For instance, the government aims to augment Ireland's MPA network from 2.13% to 30% of Ireland's maritime area by 2030, underscoring a dedication to surmounting challenges and continually enhancing marine protection policies.

As one of the planners noted during interviews, *"I think the current regime is adaptive. If you are talking about the Habitats Directive, then it is not adaptive, but the new MPA bill, I think it should be. It is designed to have an adaptive management. It is the structure of the bell. It is the process of having the stakeholders on board and having this cyclical plan. We are going to work on a six yearly cycle for revisions but with three yearly reporting. So we will be monitoring it all"*. In conclusion, the reflexivity and adaptive capacity of the existing MSP and MPA policies in Ireland are evident in their NMPF and

MPA's rigorous monitoring, review, and evaluation processes. These processes underscore a commitment to continuous learning and improvement, guided by past experiences. Ensuring the adaptability of the current regime and policies will also necessitate the design of systems that are inclusive, transparent, and flexible, accommodating all voices and enabling compromises to be reached.

Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas

In terms of reflexivity, the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site scores low with both MSP- and MPA-related actors reporting different problems in implementing adaptive strategies. The challenge of realising a more adaptive form of governance appears to run deep, with a PA government official noting that: *“To undertake assessment measures [for MPA management], you need to have Management Plans. Typically, Management Plans should be monitored every five years to assess their effectiveness, identify areas for improvement, and replicate successful approaches in other regions. The prevailing issue in our country lies in the absence of Management Plans in numerous PAs”*. In certain MPAs, the absence of Management Plans is compensated through yearly management plans prepared by the Management Units. While these plans are revised yearly, adhering to the principles of adaptive management, they still lack sufficient institutional support. The same goes for MSP, where according to Law 4759/2020 *“The competent authority... conducts a periodic assessment of maritime spatial planning every five years, by preparing an evaluation report, which determines whether revisions are necessary. Additionally, a review is mandatory at least every ten years”*. Still, while the legislative framework for MSP is in place, its practical implantation is yet to be observed.

Employee shortfall is another factor undermining the adaptive capacity of government bodies. A PA government official commented that *“there is a lack of personnel, meaning that we essentially operate reactively rather than proactively with proper planning, which hinders reflective actions or adaptation to policies through a systematic approach”*. The main challenges in formulating and implementing PA policy within the planning site revolve around the lack of knowledge concerning the marine realm and the absence of a robust institutional framework. The neglect of environmental protection is also viewed as an obstacle, as highlighted by a PA government official: *“Biodiversity protection, particularly when it clashes with investments, does not rank high on the political agenda of any government”*.

Concerning MSP, there are concerns about effectively integrating the rapidly evolving global changes and the swiftly adopted regulations into national planning. A SP government official discussed that *“The European Union continually adopts new directives and... integrating them directly [into national policy] poses some difficulties. Additionally, a significant challenge lies in effectively bridging the gap between the local, national, and regional levels of policy coordination”*. Moreover, large-scale changes like climate change and invasive species are recognized as issues of concern. However, due to the different temporal scales of these processes compared to management efforts, it becomes imperative to invest in scientific research and capacity building for successful adaptation.

Southern North Sea

As MSP remains a young process and policy even in Northern Europe, proper reflexive and adaptive capacity is difficult. In Germany, the second MSP was made by looking at what happened with the first one and learning from it to design the second one. In Belgium, there is a formal annual meeting with the governmental committees to assess the state of implementation of the MSP and discuss how

things are going. Monitoring of activities is also still in its beginnings. In Germany, a monitoring and evaluation strategy is currently under discussion. In Belgium, monitoring of the MSP currently relies on two other policies and monitoring strategies: the MSFD and the NATURA 2000 ones, and the N2000 does not have a monitoring strategy yet so it is making use of available data from other programs (including the MSFD).

Lack of space, contradictory objectives and complexity of the policy system are cited in both Belgium and Germany as major challenges in the MSP process. The BPNS is very small when compared to its neighbours, while the German part of the North Sea is small proportionally regarding its population size. Yet both areas are heavily and intensively used. In addition, EU strategies and goals are demanding and can be contradictory, especially regarding offshore wind farm development and nature conservation and restoration. Ocean multi-use might provide some solutions and is being investigated in both countries, but budgets are limited and decisions must be made that prioritize one over the other. Finally, both Germany and Belgium are federal states that already deal with different levels of policy-making and the distribution of competencies that must be aligned throughout all levels. With EU competencies on top of it, with fisheries being a European competency, the complexity of the system is a barrier to dealing with users of the sea and reaching economic, environmental and sustainable objectives.

In the Netherlands, monitoring of the MSP plan is currently done through an already implemented monitoring scheme, although initially targeting other policies. These programs are the following: the MWTL (National Surface Water Monitoring Program), the WOT (statutory research tasks), WOZEP (Offshore Wind Ecological Program) and strategic research programs of knowledge institutions (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). In addition, a new monitoring program is under elaboration, the MONS (Monitoring, Research, Nature Enhancement and Species Protection Program), meant to be an integrated assessment of the North Sea to ensure that its use remains within the ecosystem carrying capacity (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). Adaptive planning is well envisioned in the Dutch MSP, amendments to the adopted policy and management may be required as a result of new insights from monitoring, new (scientific) knowledge, new national and international regulations, strategies and objectives (Government of the Netherlands, 2022).

In England, the MMO is responsible for the monitoring strategy for East England marine plans, the following rules must followed by them, as stated by the English Marine and Coastal Access Act. At the latest three years after marine plans are implemented, the MMO must report on the spatial policy's effectiveness in achieving the areas' objective. If the results of the assessment require it, the plans should be amended or replaced. Every six years, plans for modification or replacement of marine plans must be reported to the government by the MMO (HM Government, 2014).

West Mediterranean

There is an increasing effort to better evaluate the international FRAs already defined in the basin. In 2023, the GFCM has defined guidelines for minimum monitoring and evaluation processes to be implemented in all Mediterranean FRAs, which will be approved next November 2023. They will try to overcome some previously detected limits, for example, not all the FRAs had a specific monitoring program, and sometimes they did not have a regular evaluation of their success in achieving FRAs objectives. As a consequence, their evaluation was done on an ad-hoc basis sometimes with not enough information. The new FRAs procedures include regular revisions of the results, clear monitoring systems and adopting a more adaptive approach. Nevertheless, some challenges still

remain in the GFCM marine planning, i.e., compliance mechanisms in the GFCM context need to be largely improved and data collection needs to be reinforced and further harmonized. Another interesting element of reflexivity in the context of the GFCM is that from past experiences, they have seen that it is better to integrate spatial measures into broader multiannual plans that include revisions every three years to ensure the objectives are fulfilled. In the context of the WestMed initiative, there is a five-year evaluation process that includes the evaluation of all their processes and objectives. Up to now only one revision (2017-2022) has been done and at that point, the MSP and conservation objectives were not part of the agenda, so it is not clear yet how the evaluation will take place in the context of the next five years period where both elements will be much more relevant.

Regarding the National Spatial Planning processes in place, in the Spanish case three months ago it was approved the first version of the National Marine Planning Areas. As a consequence, the process of evaluation is still in its first steps. The new plan includes an evaluation process, with yearly reports on the implementation that is starting to be developed. Interviewers point out as a challenge of the first version of the MSP the lack of a clear roadmap on how to implement the participation processes further than the minimums established by law, which from the technical perspective are considered to be too limited. As part of a self-evaluation of the implementation processes, they have decided to already contract a consultancy to develop in the near future a guideline for future MSP processes. Regarding the adaptive approach, they have decided to align the timings of the next revision of the MSP with the Marine Strategy Directive Good Environmental Status (GES) report. They consider that there are very important synergies between both processes in terms of data gathering and that it will help to ensure that MSP is adapted to support the implementation of GES. In Spanish, in relation to the tension between adaptation and stability, the interviewed pointed out *“Stakeholders ask us to achieve an equilibrium between adaptation and stability, because they cannot change easily their business plans once the investment has started, this is one of the reasons we have decided to review the MSP every six years. Not ten as the law allow us, but less, because then there will be too many changes”*.

Western Baltic Sea

Both the Danish and the German MSPs are subjected to re-evaluation after 5-years. In parallel, several monitoring initiatives in both countries produce data on the environmental state. In Germany, a monitoring and evaluation strategy is currently under discussion. However, monitoring and MSP are not coordinated to measure the effectiveness of the marine spatial plans to date. Neither is there an unambiguous definition of effectiveness due to the multi-user nature of the sea region. This includes the lack of priorities, for example, ecological or economic targets. In addition, strong competition for space among diverse and partly conflicting stakeholder interests, contradictory objectives and complexity of the national and EU policy system are cited in both Denmark and Germany as major challenges in the MSP process to reach economic, environmental and sustainable objectives.

3.5 CONCLUSIONS

A number of conclusions can be drawn when considering the current operationalisation of marine governance in the Planning Sites. What is noticeable is that, despite the various contextual issues that may be affecting the sites, there are several opportunities and challenges that appear to be broadly applicable to multiple Planning Sites.

Azores

The governance in the Azores is hindered by the fact that 3 different levels of governance and decision-making are involved and have to be taken into account: EU, national (mainland Portugal, central government) and regional (Azores regional government). In the case of the maritime governance in the Azores, in many instances, there is one piece of legislation that englobes several topics (contrary to how it is organized in many EU countries where there is a piece of legislation separated from each of the topics). For example, Decree 15/2012/A. It represents the advantage of centralizing all legislative aspects into a few legislations, but has the drawback that it also leads to problems due to the fact that to alter it all entities that relate to the piece of legislation must be contacted and actively engaged, which greatly increases complexity. Another issue relates to MSP and marine conservation, which have different meanings and different understandings for different stakeholders. Most Azorean MPAs have had little success in attaining conservation or restoration objectives. Although it falls beyond the scope of this Deliverable report, the work of Abecassis et al. (2015) thoroughly discusses this topic and provides a reflection on possible ways forward to increase the success of such area-based management tools.

Bay of Biscay

Comparing the policy processes of Spain and France in the context of MPAs and MSPs, the creation and management of MPAs in Spain were established by Law 42/2007 on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity and later complemented by Law 41/2010 for the protection of the marine environment. The RAMPE (Network of MPAs in Spain) was formally created and regulated by Law 41/2010. Additionally, Spain developed national MSP processes within the framework of National Marine Strategies for each of its five marine demarcations. In France, the national strategy for the creation and management of MPAs was developed in 2012 and transposed the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020 and its 20 Aichi Targets into its national biodiversity strategy. The National Strategy for Protected Areas 2030 covers the period 2020-2030 and deals with the expansion and qualitative management of the network. France uses "Sea basin strategic documents" (DSF) as the main tools to implement MSP. In Spain, the responsibility for preparing and managing MPAs lies with the General State Administration, together with the competent coastal Autonomous Communities. The Ministry for the Ecological Transition (MITECO) plays a role in relation to the RAMPE.

In France, the French Biodiversity Agency (FBA) under the Ministry of Ecological Transition leads the development and implementation of the national strategy for the creation and management of MPAs. PatriNat, the French national database on natural heritage, provides scientific and technical support. Spain's MSP process involves inter-administrative coordination through several collegiate bodies, including the Inter-ministerial Commission for Marine Strategies (CIEM) and Monitoring Committees for coordination with the Autonomous Communities. Spain also engages in cross-border cooperation

with France and other neighbouring Member States through expert groups, the MSP Platform, and other initiatives. France's MSP process involves coordination between the Secretary of State for the Sea, the National Committee for the Sea and Shorelines, and other relevant authorities. France also engages in cross-border cooperation with Spain and other neighbouring countries through various meetings and consultations. Spain emphasizes the importance of scientific information, such as the High Potential Zones (ZAP) for biodiversity conservation, even if they are not formal protection figures. Spain's MSP process includes environmental information, including data on national MPAs. France relies on scientific expertise from organizations like REMA and CEREMA to conduct research, develop methodologies, and provide guidance for MSP processes. Overall, both Spain and France have established legal frameworks for the creation and management of MPAs and have integrated MSP processes into their marine strategies. Both countries emphasize the importance of scientific knowledge and engage in cross-border cooperation to ensure consistency and coordination in marine planning. However, they differ in the specific entities responsible for MPA management and MSP implementation.

Comparing the participation and stakeholder influence in Spain and France in the context of MPAs and MSPs, Spain had planned workshops or participatory events with representatives from key economic sectors to involve them in the development of the national MSP. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the in-person events were cancelled, and an online meeting was held instead, with over 270 participants representing different sectors. In France, there is a formal consultation process with stakeholders and the general public as part of the MSP development. The process involves the National Council for Public Debates and the National Committee organizing public debates, consultations, and workshops. This two-stage process includes extensive consultations with stakeholders. In Spain, the consultation process started in January 2020 with the General Directorate for Environmental Quality and Evaluation seeking contributions from affected public administrations and interested individuals on the draft plan and initial strategic document. Additional consultations with affected public administrations and interested parties took place from July 2021 to September 2021. In France, the formal consultation of stakeholders and the general public takes place ahead of the planning and when the planning is ready, involving two stages. The National Council for Public Debates is consulted if they want to organize a public debate, and the National Committee handles the consultation process when the planning is ready. In Spain, the participation process involved thematic ad-hoc groups/meetings with non-sectorial stakeholders, autonomous community administrations (i.e., local governments), and initiatives demanded by specific sectors (e.g., marine renewable energies and fishermen).

Different levels of engagement were organized, including technical and high-political level meetings. In France, the Coordinator Prefects support the secretariat of the Conseils Maritimes de Façade, a consultative organism that brings together around 80 stakeholders representing various national authorities, local and regional authorities, blue economy companies, trade unions, and NGOs. In Spain, after considering all the allegations received through the consultation processes, all involved sectors in Spain, except the fishing sector, agreed with the final version of the national MSP. The marine renewable energy industry expressed concern about the reduction of polygons for their activities. In France, the maritime council in France is permanent and oversees the entire MSP process and its implementation. The formal consultation process involves consultations and workshops, which can be resource-intensive. In summary, both Spain and France prioritize stakeholder involvement in their MSP processes, with similar approaches and methods. Spain initially planned in-person participatory events but had to adapt to online meetings due to the pandemic. France, on the other hand, has a formal consultation process involving public debates, consultations, and workshops. Both countries seek input from various stakeholders, but the level and timing of engagement differ. In the end,

stakeholders' feedback and influence can vary, as seen in the differing responses from the fishing and marine renewable energy sectors in Spain. Apart from sharing information, there is no cooperation in decision-making.

Comparing the reflexivity and adaptive capacity aspects of MSP, both countries demonstrate reflexivity in their MSP processes by incorporating evaluation, monitoring, and assessment mechanisms, aiming to effectively manage their marine spaces in alignment with environmental objectives and the needs of various sectors. Both countries show adaptive capacity in their MSP processes by considering long-term objectives and using data-driven approaches. Spain ensures involvement and investment through long-term sector objectives, while France benefits from CEREMA's tools and guidelines for adaptive decision-making. In Spain, the national MSP is closely linked to Spanish Marine Strategies, while in France, the Secretary of State for the Sea takes on the overall planning responsibility. Spain's MSP undergoes review and updates every six years, coinciding with the cycle reviews of Spanish Marine Strategies (as required by the MSFD).

Campania

In Italy, the current state of internal legislation on the management of the sea and the protection of the marine environment is very complex, poorly coordinated and requires a difficult reconstructive effort to understand to which extent Italy across the levels of institutions effectively guarantee the protection and management by of its natural marine resources. Both the horrendogram and the organogram reflect the hierarchical complexity of the policies applied to the management of the marine environment in Italy and more specifically in the Campania Region. Italy adopts and implements in its national legislation the EU policy concerning the protection and management of the marine environment including the regulation EU 2014/89 on MSP, but one important issue besides their formal implementation is the control of the territory, an issue that is particularly relevant in the Natura 2000 sites still lacking a real management.

A national MSP has been developed but not yet formally approved. It provides also for the Campania region guidelines to be used as a reference for other planning actions (sector or local level) and the granting of concessions or authorisations. Depending on the characteristics of the sub-areas and planning needs, the Plan provides more or less detailed indications, both in terms of spatial resolution and in terms of definition of measures and recommendations. However, it has been stressed the difficulty in data access and environmental data sharing, represents a potential limit in an efficient MSP process. A Technical Committee at the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, which includes five central Administrations and the Maritime Regions, was the competent authority for drafting the plan. At the local level, the Region Campania was responsible for the involvement of local stakeholders. Regarding the protection of the marine environment, the MPAs were not formally consulted in the process. Once the Plan has been approved, the future development of conservation measures in the Campania SP, including the achievement of European conservation objectives, will have to take into account the specific features of the Plan and therefore the uses of the sea established for the various areas. The MPAs applied an ecosystem-based and adaptive management approach in their competence areas. It appears however that there is a weak interaction among MPAs at a national and regional Mediterranean scale and their contribution to the global protection of marine biodiversity at different spatial scales is not yet fully understood. The different Italian administrative regions, including Campania, deal with the overall management of the territorial system of protected areas and Natura 2000 (Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC) network sites by adopting recommendations and laws for their establishment, and their planning and management. It is interesting to mention that

one of the interviewed Directors stressed that the biggest challenge is the need to consider the sea as a territory, not a “panorama”. If it were a territory, we have the obligation to apply the territory regulations.

Celtic Sea

The assessment of Ireland's marine environmental policies within the Celtic Sea planning site reveals several key findings. Firstly, the effective implementation of these policies demonstrates a clear commitment to balancing economic exploitation with marine conservation efforts. The development of the National Marine Planning Framework and the impending MPA legislation reflect a strategic approach towards safeguarding marine resources. However, challenges arise from the delayed formalization of MPA legislation, potentially slowing the realization of the goal of protecting 30% of Ireland's EEZ by 2030. Stakeholder engagement plays a pivotal role in policy development and implementation. A diverse range of sectors, including environmental NGOs, professional bodies, and technical experts, actively contribute to the planning process. While efforts are made to include various stakeholders, ensuring equitable representation across all sectors can be a challenge. Additionally, a transparent and inclusive consultation process, including public events and online engagements, demonstrates a commitment to incorporating diverse perspectives. The policies showcase adaptive capacity in response to evolving demands. Economic development, particularly in ORE, acts as a catalyst for policy development. The new MPA bill is designed to be adaptive, emphasizing cyclical revisions and stakeholder involvement. This reflects a proactive approach towards overcoming challenges in policy enforcement, political will, and stakeholder divergence. The government's target to expand the MPA network underscores a dedication to continually enhancing marine protection policies. Overall, the findings highlight a dynamic institutional context, characterized by ongoing efforts to balance economic development with marine conservation measures in the Celtic Sea planning site and the wider Ireland's marine environment.

Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas

The Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site is currently facing significant policy challenges in meeting time constraints to fulfil EU obligations and address existing gaps. The absence of an operational national MSP plan and Management Plans for most MPAs is a pressing issue. However, the country is undergoing reforms and policy introductions, including the implementation of a National Maritime Spatial Strategy, Marine Spatial Frameworks, and Special Environmental Studies. These initiatives will lay the foundation for MSP implementation, delineate land/sea uses and management options within MPAs, and pave the way for their subsequent revision and expansion. Stakeholder involvement at the national level primarily occurs through formal procedures and is facilitated by funded projects undertaken by Ministries' directorates. However, concerns have been raised about the integration of scientific knowledge into decision-making processes. Positive stakeholder interactions have been observed on a smaller scale in areas where conservation initiatives and environmental management bodies have been operating for an extended period. Unfortunately, the Planning Site currently lacks the fundamental prerequisites for adopting more flexible approaches, except for some long-term established protected areas, which serve as rare examples of management reflexivity. Despite legislation advocating for adaptive strategies, challenges such as lack of political will, personnel shortages, and delays in policy adoption hinder the effective implementation of such approaches.

Southern North Sea

The countries of the SNS case study are amongst the first to have implemented a maritime spatial plan and are today at their second or third MSP, with the exception of England which updates its first plan at regular intervals. The motivation behind MSP is to coordinate the various industrial activities that make the North Sea the most industrialized sea in the world. The major economic sectors in the SNS are: oil and gas extraction, fishing, shipping, offshore wind energy production, sand extraction and aquaculture. Besides the need to coordinate all these uses and ensure socio-economic development, protection of the marine environment and reaching biodiversity and climate objectives are strong incentives behind MSP in the SNS. To achieve European climate objectives for 2050, offshore wind energy production has become a priority in all countries of the SNS, with an increase in areas allocated to that purpose. Because of its space-demanding and exclusive characteristics, the offshore wind sector conflicts with other uses, such as fishing and nature conservation. The tension between the need to address biodiversity goals and climate neutrality was mentioned by both Belgian and German policymakers. As an answer to conflict over marine space, ocean multi-use (combination of activities at sea in a single area) gains in popularity, and is explicitly advocated for in the Belgian and Dutch MSP. However, budget issues, as stated by a Belgian policymaker, remain a very real barrier to achieving all European goals and strategies. Stakeholder engagement appears to be well implemented in all four countries, with Germany being less familiar with the approach but going in that direction nonetheless. International consultation is respected, as is required by the MSP Directive, and some unofficial coordination seems to happen as well. Yet, MSP remains a tool used at a national perspective without fully considering the North Sea as one ecosystem, in need of homogeneous management.

West Mediterranean

It is necessary to highlight the great complexity of the legislation linked with marine ecosystems and MSP in the region. In some cases, there is a lack of connection between them because of the fragmentation in sectorial laws. However, from the regional perspective, we have identified two major organisations, the United Nations and the European Commission, which have a high level of commitment concerning marine ecosystem protection and MSP. According to our interviewees, EBSA areas, as currently defined, are not a major contribution to MSP in the region. As currently defined they are very broad, and according to our interviewees, it is not clear what their added value is. In a context where most of the MSP is done at the national level, stakeholders usually consider that the national MSP and MPA processes provide them with enough specific environmental information.

MSP in the region is up to now mostly done from the National Perspective, but there are an increasing number of sectorial relevant initiatives that have an international basin focus. The most important ones are linked with fisheries and secondly in transnational transport. There is not a global regional MSP taking place, and from the ecological basin perspective, it is generally not integrated at the national level. While there is a formal balance in the planning process at the regional level, there is also an imbalance in capacity between European countries and Southern Basin countries. In European countries, globally speaking stakeholders have a more influence capacity, but often their participation is reactive at the final steps of the decision-making process, and the level of influence is variable depending on the sectors. In non-European countries, there are an increasing number of MSP and MPA small initiatives but the participation processes are not clear. There is an increasing interest by southern countries in getting technical support to step up MSP processes at the national level.

There is an increasing perception in the basin of the need to develop MSP, but the general perspective is that first it should be reinforced at the national level, while at the international level, the next step forward in the short term could be in agreeing common data collecting frameworks, continue working on sectorial spatial marine processes and agreeing on common political goals. Transnational global MSP processes are only considered in the long term.

Western Baltic Sea

The Western Baltic Sea is one of the most intensely used marine regions in the world. Shipping, energy production, fishing and substrate extraction compete with ecological interest, and ecological interests are heterogeneous and uncoordinated. Conflict exists especially between fisheries and environmentalists. For Germany, the construction of new wind farms, the salvage of old munitions and the reinforcement of marine protection have become priorities, which not only lead to conflicts between these but also other sectors (e.g., fishing, tourism, shipping). In Denmark, many current protected areas have a single purpose use, and while birds are protected, fishing continues here. Since birds eat fish, the balance of the ecosystem is further disturbed and the areas might even have a counter-productive effect. These conflicts can be documented and partially measured, as we plan in this project. However, they can only be resolved politically.

4 DISCUSSION

By auditing the current institutional and policy landscape of MarinePlan's Planning Sites, this report presents insight into a range of governance-related trends, problems and opportunities. This includes an analysis of the marine environmental legislation frameworks of the Planning Sites, as well as a comparative assessment of these regions with one another. The creation of horrendograms for each region helps to illustrate the existing complexity in environmental legislation, a serious challenge that has been long debated in marine governance literature (Kelly et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2021; Stephenson et al., 2021). The horrendograms are a useful tool for identifying policy gaps and highlighting the commonality of approaches across the Planning Sites. Adding to this, the development of organogram figures for each Planning Site reflects crucial information on the organisational dynamics of how governance is operationalised.

Many regions appear to have constructed unnecessarily complex legislative and administrative frameworks, managed by a plethora of organisations and administrative bodies that attempt to respond to a suite of international, national and regional policies, laws and agreements. That lack of a single authority responsible for the management of the marine environment in each region may not be a surprising finding, yet it reinforces the inherent challenge of dealing with individual rules and policies, often with a sectoral bias. What D4.1 makes clear is that ineffective communication and a lack of coordination across institutional landscapes are prevalent, leading to a diverse range of conflicting marine activities being regulated by numerous pieces of legislation and policy. When considering the value of this report, it is worthy to suggest that these findings, especially when merged with other outputs from the MarinePlan project, could be used as a baseline for pan-European cooperation on marine governance targets and objectives.

A range of information is revealed regarding the organisation of the policy processes that underpin marine governance in each of the Planning Site areas. In doing so, it illustrates what policies are being created, what their objectives are, how they are being informed, and how they consider transboundary issues. Information is revealed regarding the networks and structures that policy-makers participate in to achieve their policy goals. Reference is also made to the emergent challenges that hinder MSP and MPA integration, as well as consideration of how these have been responded to in different contexts. Using the current status of MSP in the Azores as an example, it is demonstrated that the regional policies for the governance of the ocean are based on co-management work to promote integrated and sustainable management. Policy processes have been designed to align the interests of various political and economic agents and stakeholders, with the regional policies relying heavily on the contribution of researchers, fishers and associations of the marine sector. Portugal was one of the first Member States to undertake the MSP process, but the country was missing a specific plan for the Azores archipelago. At the time of its development, MSP in Portugal's outermost region was the responsibility of the regional government of the Azores. However, In July 2022, the Portuguese Constitutional Court mandated the central government with the exclusive responsibility for the implementation of EU maritime Directives, bypassing regional authorities' influence over the matter. A situation plan for the Azores received a non-binding favourable opinion from the Consultative Committee in July 2023 and is now being submitted to public consultation. This highlights how MSP, as with other marine policy processes, is a live and constantly evolving arena. What appears consistent across the majority of Planning Sites is that the MSP and MPAs processes are rapidly evolving, largely linked to international and European targets, objectives and agreements.

Focusing on transboundary issues, this report illustrates that a multitude of challenges continue to affect the development of MSP in cross-border regions. Using the Western Mediterranean as an example, it is clear that MSP in the region continues to be organised from a national perspective. There is no cross-cutting regional MSP taking place and, from the ecological basin perspective, transboundary objectives are not generally integrated at the national level. While there is a formal balance in the planning process at the regional level, there is also an imbalance in capacity between European countries and Southern Basin countries. In European countries, stakeholders have greater influence on the operationalisation of MSP, but their participation is often reactive at the final steps of the decision-making process and their level of influence is variable depending on the sectors. In non-European countries, there are an increasing number of small MSP and MPA initiatives, yet information on participation processes has not been clearly outlined. It is also found that there is an increasing call by southern countries in the region to receive technical support to step-up MSP processes at the national level.

A key element of this report is an illustration of how stakeholder participation is operationalised in each of the Planning Site areas. Information is provided on how external stakeholders are involved in participation processes, who the most influential stakeholders are, and how such actors exert their influence. This involves assessments of the formal consultation processes that operate, what engagement methods beyond consultation are utilised, and the degrees to which policies have changed as a result of participation processes. In the Campania region, MSP formal consultations are put in place through the MSP technical committee. This has developed internal consultations. However, it is not clear how the results of this consultation have been considered and eventually integrated into the MSP. Concerning the establishment of new MPAs, it is not an obligation to carry out formal stakeholder consultations as there is no mandatory requirement in this regard. It is the responsibility of MPA directors to promote stakeholder engagement through formal and informal processes.

In Belgium, this report reveals how public consultation is a long-standing practice and is well infused in the political culture of the country. Before the initiation of public consultation, informal exchanges happen in the making of an MSP draft. Currently, the 2026-2034 planning has started, and it was launched by a kick-off event gathering all major stakeholders. Interestingly, in Germany, which is also a part of the SNS Planning Site, public consultation is less common. In the making of the second German MSP (2021-2031), policymakers took the initiative to have an informal stakeholder consultation process. This was a rather innovative initiative for Germany and took the form of informal meetings and e-mail exchanges with relevant stakeholders. Based on this review, a first pre-draft was designed and taken into formal public consultation. From a comparative perspective, it is evident that each of the Planning Sites' stakeholder participation processes represent varying levels of robustness. There is limited evidence of genuine co-development within MSP and MPA processes, with some small examples to the contrary, with several indications of power imbalances existing between stakeholders. This includes differing levels of stakeholder influence being exerted on decision-making. Although a further examination of the topic of co-development in relation to governance arrangements falls beyond the scope of D4.1, it is a theme that will be critically assessed in D4.2 (an assessment of how current governance regimes valorise and use diverse knowledge on conservation measures and MSP processes). What the findings of this report highlight is the need to design participation frameworks and strategies that are genuinely open, inclusive and responsive to the needs of stakeholders. This is particularly needed as MSP and MPA processes continue to evolve at a rapid pace.

A further finding of this report relates to how the effectiveness of the current policy is being monitored and reviewed across the Planning Sites. These findings illustrate how evaluation processes are conducted, what this suggests about the adaptive capacity of policy-makers, and if previous successes (or failures) have informed change in the regions. The information presented includes insight into the degree to which formal monitoring or evaluation approaches are used to measure the impact of policies relating to MSP and MPAs, and how these are operationalised. There is also interesting information revealed regarding the major challenges that have been encountered in the past when developing new marine governance policies and how these have impacted policy development. In the Celtic Sea Planning site, as an example, the effectiveness of current MSP and MPA policies undergo formal monitoring and review. Both the marine planning framework and MPA legislation in Ireland incorporate provisions for stakeholder participation, which are integral to their respective review processes. These evaluation procedures engage advisory groups established by the government. These groups offer independent expert advice and recommendations for expanding Ireland's MPA network and implementing the national marine planning framework. Such processes reflect a high degree of adaptive capacity among policy-makers, actively seeking input and insights from stakeholders. In terms of reflexivity in the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site, it is revealed that the region scores low with both MSP- and MPA-related actors reporting different problems in implementing adaptive strategies. The challenge of realising a more adaptive form of governance appears to run deep. In certain MPAs, the absence of management plans is compensated through yearly management plans prepared by the relevant management units. While these plans are revised yearly, adhering to the principles of adaptive management, they continue to lack sufficient institutional support. It is demonstrated that the same goes for MSP in the region. While the legislative framework for MSP is in place, its practical implantation is yet to be observed.

5 NEXT STEPS

This Deliverable report represents the first output of WP4. In and of itself, the report is an insightful overview of the key opportunities and challenges facing marine governance across multiple European regions. The report will be used to directly inform the remaining tasks in Work Package 4, as well as providing vital information regarding the governance and policy landscapes of each Planning Site that will contribute to other objectives within the MarinePlan project. The second task of Work Package 4, Task 4.2, will build on the findings presented in this report by exploring how non-government stakeholders are influencing the governance frameworks of each Planning Site. Elements of D4.1 will be used to guide how Task 4.2 assesses the adaptive capacity of existing governance regimes and examines how knowledge is used to inform conservation measures and MSP processes. Furthermore, the findings presented in D4.1 regarding co-development within governance processes will contribute significant insight that will complement other MarinePlan tasks. By demonstrating how co-development varies across institutional contexts, the policy recommendations and solutions proposed by MarinePlan can be tailored to match the individual conditions of each Planning Site. Thus, D4.1 represents not only a valuable audit of existing policies and institutions across multiple European regions, but also a vital resource that will help to inform the development of MarinePlan's practical outputs.

6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abecasis, R.C., Afonso, P., Colaço, A., Longnecker, N., Clifton, J., Schmidt, L. and Santos, R.S., 2015. Marine conservation in the Azores: evaluating marine protected area development in a remote island context. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 2: 104. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2015.00104>
- Alloncle, N., Bliard, F., Campillos-Llanos, M., CerveraNúñez, C., De Magalhães, A. V., Fauveau, G., Gimard, A., Giret, O., Gómez-Ballesteros, M., Lloret, A., Lopes Alves, F., Mahier, M., Marques, M., Murciano, C., Odion, M., Piel, S., Quintela, A., and Sousa, L., 2019. Marine protected areas in OSPAR region IV: Bay of Biscay and Iberian coast - Database completion and analysis. EU Project Grant No.: EASME/EMFF/2015/1.2.1.3/03/SI2.742089. Supporting Implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning in the Northern European Atlantic (SIMNORAT). French Agency for Biodiversity. 31 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2597299>.
- Borja, A., Amouroux, D., Anschutz, P., Gomez-Gesteira, M., Uyarra, M.C., and Valdes, L., 2019. The Bay of Biscay, in: C. Sheppard (Ed.), *World Seas: an Environmental Evaluation* (second ed.), 5: 113-152, Academic Press.
- Boyes, S.J. and Elliott, M., 2014. Marine Legislation – the ultimate ‘horrendogram’: International Law, European Directives & National Implementation. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 86(1-2): 39-47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.055>.
- Boyes, S.J. and Elliott, M., 2015. The Excessive Complexity of National Marine Governance Systems – Has This Decreased in England Since the Introduction of the Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009? *Marine Policy*, 51: 57-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.07.019>.
- Calado, H., Borges, P., Phillips, M., Ng, K. and Alves, F., 2011. The Azores archipelago, Portugal: improved understanding of small island coastal hazards and mitigation measures. *Natural Hazards*, 58: 427-444. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-010-9676-5/>
- Cantasano, N., Pellicone, G., and Ietto, F., 2017. Integrated coastal zone management in Italy: a gap between science and policy. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 21: 317-325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-016-0479-z>
- Carvalho, N., Edwards-Jones, G. and Isidro, E., 2011. Defining scale in fisheries: Small versus large-scale fishing operations in the Azores. *Fisheries Research*, 109(2-3): 360-369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2011.03.006>
- Clarke, V., Braun, V. and Hayfield, N., 2015. Thematic analysis. *Qualitative psychology: A practical guide to research methods*, 3: 222-248. <http://digital.casalini.it/9781473933415>
- Claudet, J., Loiseau, C., Sostres, M., & Zupan M. 2020. Underprotected Marine Protected Areas in a Global Biodiversity Hotspot. *One Earth*, 2: 380-384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.03.008>
- Coll, M., Cury, P., Azzurro, E., Bariche, M., Bayadas, G., Bellido, J.M., Chaboud, C., Claudet, J., El-Sayed, A., Gascuel, D., Knittweis, L., Pipitone, C., Samuel-Rhoads, Y., Taleb, S., Tudela, S., and Valls, A.

2013. The scientific strategy needed to promote a regional ecosystem-based approach to fisheries in the Mediterranean and Black Seas. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries*, 23: 415-434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-013-9305-y>
- Cormier, R., Elliott, M., and Borja, Á., 2022. Managing Marine Resources Sustainably – The ‘Management Response-Footprint Pyramid’ Covering Policy, Plans and Technical Measures. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. 9:869992. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.869992>.
- Diogo, H., Pereira, J.G., Higgins, R.M., Canha, Â. and Reis, D., 2015. History, effort distribution and landings in an artisanal bottom longline fishery: An empirical study from the North Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Policy*, 51, pp.75-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.07.022>
- Elliott, M., Borja, A., and Cormier, R., 2020. Activity-footprints, pressures-footprints and effects-footprints – walking the pathway to determining and managing human impacts in the sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 155: 111201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111201>.
- Elliott, M., Boyes, S.J. and Cormier, R., 2022. Natural England – Discussion Document - Governance and Achievement of Good Environmental Status. Report to Natural England, UK by IECS Ltd.
- FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2019a. Royal Decree establishing the marine spatial planning for the period 2020 to 2026 in the Belgian sea-areas. Available at: <https://www.health.belgium.be/en/royal-decree-msp-2020-english-courtesy-translation>
- FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2019b. Annexe 2 Vision à long terme, objectifs et indicateurs, et choix stratégiques en matière d’aménagement PAEM 2020. Available at: <https://www.health.belgium.be/fr/annexe-2-paem-vision-long-terme-objectifs-et-indicateurs-et-choix-strategiques-en-matiere>
- Government of Ireland, 2023. National Marine Planning Framework Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/a4a9a-national-marine-planning-framework/>. Accessed on: 27th September 2023.
- Government of the Netherlands, 2022. North Sea Programme 2022-2027, annex to the National Water Programme 2022-2027. Available at: <https://www.noordzeeloket.nl/en/policy/north-sea-programme-2022-2027/>
- Hervann, P.Y., Gascuel, D., Grüss, A., Druon, J.N., Kopp, D., Perez, I., Piroddi, C. and Robert, M., 2020. The Celtic Sea Through Time and Space: Ecosystem Modeling to Unravel Fishing and Climate Change Impacts on Food-Web Structure and Dynamics. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7:578717. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.578717>
- HM Government, 2014. East Inshore and East Offshore Marine Plans. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/east-inshore-and-east-offshore-marine-plans>
- Katsanevakis, S., Levin, N., Coll, M., Giakoumi, S., Shkedi, D., Mackelworth, P., Frascchetti, S., Levy, R., Velegrakis, A., Koutsoubas, D., Caric, H., Brokovich, E., Ozturk, B., and Kark, S., 2015. Marine conservation challenges in an era of economic crisis and geopolitical instability: The case of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Policy*, 51: 31-39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.07.013>

- Kelly, C., Ellis, G. and Flannery, W., 2019. Unravelling persistent problems to transformative marine governance. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, p.213. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00213>
- Lewison, R., Hobday, A.J., Maxwell, S., Hazen, E., Hartog, J.R., Dunn, D.C., Briscoe, D., Fossette, S., O'Keefe, C.E., Barnes, M. and Abecassis, M., 2015. Dynamic ocean management: identifying the critical ingredients of dynamic approaches to ocean resource management. *BioScience*, 65(5): 486-498. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biv018>
- Ministero delle infrastrutture e della mobilità sostenibili, 2022. I Piani dello Spazio Marittimo italiani Area Marittima "Tirreno-Mediterraneo Occidentale". Sintesi.
- MMO, 2013. East Inshore and East Offshore Marine Plan Areas Evidence and Issues, Overview Report 2012. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/312393/east_evidence_issues_overview.pdf
- MMO, 2013. Marine Planning Decision Makers' Workshops, Summary report, December 2013. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/312486/east-decision-makers.pdf
- Monwar, M., Tzika, E., Magalhães, A.V., Grimmel, H., Moniz, F., Bonnon, M. and Calado, H., 2020. Analysis and Comparison of the Legal Frameworks of the North Atlantic Countries. WP and Task 1: International Legal and Political Framework. GPSAZORES GPS Azores – Geographical and Political Scenarios and Maritime Spatial Planning for the Azores and North Atlantic. Available at: https://www.gpsazores.com/media/GPSAzores_Report_WP1_ntVEqu9.pdf
- National Parks Wildlife Service, 2023. Protected sites in Ireland. Available at: <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/>. Accessed on: 27th September 2023.
- O'Higgins T., O'Higgins L., O'Hagan A.M., Ansong J.O., 2019. Challenges and opportunities for ecosystem-based management and marine spatial planning in the Irish Sea. In: Zaucha J. and Gee, K. (Eds.) *Maritime spatial planning: past, present, future*. Pp. 47–69. Springer Nature: Cambridge, UK.
- Pascual, M., Borja, A., Galparsoro, I., Ruiz, J., Mugerza, E., Quincoces, I., Murillas, A., and Arregi, L., 2013. Total fishing pressure produced by artisanal fisheries, from a Marine Spatial Planning perspective: a case study from the Basque Country (Bay of Biscay), *Fisheries Research*, 147: 240–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2013.06.010>
- Pınarbaşı, K., Galparsoro, I., Alloncle, N., Quemmerais, F., and Borja, Á., 2020. Key issues for a transboundary and ecosystem-based Maritime Spatial Planning in the Bay of Biscay. *Marine Policy*, 120, 104131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104131>
- Reimann, L., Vafeidis, A.T., Brown, S., Hinkel, J., and Tol, R.S., 2018. Mediterranean UNESCO World Heritage at risk from coastal flooding and erosion due to sea-level rise. *Nature communications*, 9, 4161. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06645-9>

- Regione Campania, 2022. Piano di utilizzazione delle Aree Demaniali Marittime ad uso turistico-ricreativo (PUAD).
- Repubblica Italiana, 2016. DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 17 ottobre 2016, n. 201. Attuazione della direttiva 2014/89/UE che istituisce un quadro per la pianificazione dello spazio marittimo. (16G00215)
- Singh, G.G., Cottrell, R.S., Eddy, T.D. and Cisneros-Montemayor, A.M., 2021. Governing the land-sea interface to achieve sustainable coastal development. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, p.709947. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.709947>
- Stephenson, R.L., Hobday, A.J., Allison, E.H., Armitage, D., Brooks, K., Bundy, A., Cvitanovic, C., Dickey-Collas, M., Grilli, N.D.M., Gomez, C. and Jarre, A., 2021. The quilt of sustainable ocean governance: patterns for practitioners. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, p.630547. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.630547>
- Terry, G., Hayfield, N., Clarke, V. and Braun, V., 2017. Thematic analysis. In: Willig, C. and Stainton Rogers, W. (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research in psychology*, 2, pp. 17-37.
- The Federal Law Gazette, 2021. Spatial Plan for the German Exclusive Economic Zone in the North Sea and in the Baltic Sea. Annex to the Spatial Planning Ordinance for the German exclusive economic zone in the North Sea and in the Baltic Sea dated 19 August 2021, unofficial translation. Available at: https://www.bsh.de/EN/TOPICS/Offshore/Maritime_spatial_planning/Maritime_Spatial_Plan_2021/Anlagen/Downloads/ROP_2021/Maritime_Spatial_Plan_2021.pdf?blob=publicationFile&v=5
- Torta, G., 2023. Il delicato equilibrio tra la tutela dell'ambiente e la promozione delle attività economiche nella pianificazione dello spazio marino. *Ambientediritto. IT*, (1): 1-21.

7 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AA - Appropriate Assessments
AARHUS Conv. - UNECE Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters
AICHI Targets - 20 biodiversity targets to help reach 6 main goals of the CBD
BERN Conv. - Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (1979)
BONN Conv. - The Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals
BWD - Bathing Waters Directive
BWM - Ballast Water Management Convention
CBD - Convention on Biological Diversity
CITES - Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
Conv. - Convention
COP - Conference of the Parties
COP9 - 9th meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity 2008, adopted the scientific criteria for identifying EBSAs
COP15 - 15th UN Biodiversity Conference, Canada 2022
COP26 - 26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26), Glasgow 2021; similarly COP27 for Egypt 2022
COTES - Control of Trade in Endangered Species Regulations
CSIC - Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas
DG SANTE - Directorate General for Health and Food Safety
DRAM - Regional Directorate for Maritime Affairs
DSS – Decision Support System

DTU - Denmarks Tekniske Universitet
EBSAs - Ecologically or Biologically significant Marine Areas in need of protection in open-ocean waters and deep-sea habitats
EB-MSP - Ecosystem-Based Maritime Spatial Planning
EEZ - Exclusive Economic Zone
EFH - Essential Fish Habitats
EIA - Environmental Impact Assessment
EMS - European Marine Sites
ESPOO - Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment in a Transboundary Context
EU - European Union
FAO - Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FCS - Favourable Conservation Status
FRA - Fisheries Restricted Areas
FRMD - Flood Risk Management Directive
GES - Good Environmental Status
HBD - Habitat and Bird Directives
HMWBs - Heavily Modified Water Bodies
HPMA - Highly Protected Marine Area
HRA - Habitat Regulations Assessments
HSD - Habitats and Species Directive
ICES - International Council for the Exploration of the Seas
IECS - International Estuarine & Coastal Specialists
IMAR - Instituto Do Mar
IMO - International Maritime Organisation

ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambiente
Kyoto Protocol - Operationalises the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
MAR - Mid-Atlantic Ridge
MARPOL- International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution by Ships
MASE - Ministry of Environment and Energy Security
MCZs - Marine Conservation Zones
MI - Marine Institute
MPA - Marine Protected Area
MSFD - Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP - Maritime Spatial Planning
MSP Dir. - Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
Natura 2000 - A network of nature protection areas made up of SACs and SPAs
NPWS - National Parks Wildlife Service
NSIPs - Nationally Strategic Infrastructure Projects
OECD - Convention on the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development – OECD Country
OECMs - Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures
ORE - Offshore Renewable Energy
OSPAR - The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North East Atlantic
PSSA - Particularly Sensitive Sea Area – designated under IMO Resolution A.982(24)
QUB - Queen's University Belfast
RAMSAR Conv. - Intergovernmental treaty that provides the framework for the conservation and wise use of wetlands and their resources, Ramsar 1971

RBINS - Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
RBMP - River Basin Management Plans
RFMOs - Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
Reg(s) - Regulations
SAC - Special Area of Conservation
SEA - Strategic Environmental Assessment
SNS - The Southern North Sea
SNZ - Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn
SPA - Special Protection Area
TAC - Total Allowable Catches
UAEGEAN - Panepistimio Aigaiouhttps
UHAM - Universität Hamburg
UN - United Nations
UNCLOS - United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UN DER - United Nations Decade of Ecosystem Restoration 2021-2030
UN DOS - United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainability 2021-2030
UNECE - United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNEP - United Nations Environment Programme
UN FAO - United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation
UNFCCC - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNGA - United Nations General Assembly
UNINA - Università Degli Studi Di Napoli Federico II
UN SDG - United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
UWWTD - Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive

VME - Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (UN FAO)
WBD - Wild Birds Directive
WFD - Water Framework Directive
WHS - World Heritage Site
WR - Stichting Wageningen Research